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Study of thermochemical co-treatment of seafood by-products and green waste towards alternative fertilizer production within Horizon2020 SEA2LAND

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to Daddy,
you "have only slipped away into the next room"

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Abstract

In recent years the expansion of the fish processing industry caused by the increase in seafood consumption has led to a considerable increase in by-products (up to 70%), causing important management problems due to their degree of degradability. However, they can be valorised as bio-products for agriculture as they are rich in nutrients, especially nitrogen, and others, representing a good opportunity to mitigate the environmental problems associated with their disposal.

In this context, in the frame of SEA2LAND project, the possibility to recover bio-based fertilizer from molluscs and fish wastes has been studied. These wastes were collected, respectively, from the local companies Co.Pe.Mo. and Ittica del Conero, to be then applied in agriculture as soil improvers or organic fertilizers, which is completely in line with the objective set by the European Commission to reduce the use of non-renewable sources in fertilizer production by 30%. The valorization technologies which were experimentally investigated in this study consisted of pyrolysis and composting with biochar addition. Legislative requirements and international quality standards were also analysed and taken into account.

As first step, lab-scale pyrolysis was performed in order to analyze the biochar obtained from different sources and assess its compliance with quality standards. Tests were carried out by mixing gardening waste, commonly used in pyrolysis due to the lignocellulosic matrix, and fish by-products. Results showed non-significant differences in the char produced at a physical level, but at a chemical level, a significant increase in the nitrogen content in the pyrolysed biomass with higher percentages of fish by-products was observed. However, at the same time an increase in the nickel content, exceeding the threshold values given by quality standards was also obtained. Analyses were also performed on the bio-oil and syngas produced during pyrolysis to understand how the presence of lignocellulosic material can interact with the fish.

After that, fish by-products were composted in a 30-L reactor with forced aeration by adding 10% of biochar to improve process performance such as the increase in biological activity, reduction of odor and GHG emissions, and minimization of Nitrogen loss. The temperature inside the reactor, oxygen and carbon dioxide in exhausted gas were monitored online as an indication of microbial activity and control of aeration strategy. Composting mixture was sampled once per week to determine the degree of biological stability and control process performance. The ammonia emissions produced during the test were compared to other composting tests performed without the addition of biochar, showing a significant reduction. It was corroborated by performing nitrogen mass balances that the addition of biochar within the feedstock to be composted significantly reduced emissions, thus increasing the nitrogen content within the final product, which can improve its value as N-fertilizer.

1. Introduction

1.1. Statement of the problem

Global fish production has been estimated in about 179 million tons (Mt) in 2018 and is projected to reach 200 Mt by 2029 (OECD-FAO, 2020). Of the total, in 2018, 156 million tons were used for human consumption, equivalent to an estimated annual supply of 20.5 kg per capita per year, while the remaining 23 million tons were destined for non-food uses, mainly to produce fishmeal and fish oil (FAO, 2020)

Marine seafood includes finfish (pollock, tuna, herring, mackerel, whiting, and others), crustaceans such as shrimp, krill, crab, and lobster, bivalves including mussels, oysters, clams, and scallops, cephalopods such as squid and cuttlefish. The seafood industry comprises both capture fisheries and aquaculture (Venugopal & Sasidharan, 2021). Aquaculture production is projected to reach 105 Mt by 2029, 10 Mt more than the capture sector (OECD-FAO, 2020). Today aquaculture is by far the dominant source of bivalve molluscs: in 2018, shelled molluscs (17.3 Mt) represented 56.3% of the production of marine and coastal aquaculture, finfish (7.3 Mt) and crustaceans (5.7 Mt) taken together were responsible for 42.5%, while the rest consisted of other aquatic animals (FAO, 2020).

The increasing consumption of fish has led to an expansion of the fish processing industry which in turn has resulted in increasing quantities of by-products, which may represent up to 70% of processed fish. These by-products are usually composed of heads (which represent 9-12% of total fish weight), viscera (12-18%), skin (1-3%), bones (9-15%) and scales (about 5%). In the case of mollusc waste, it includes molluscs not suitable for the market, since they are undersized, fouled with barnacles, broken shells or unwanted species.

The increase in fish by-products causes important management problems, as fish wastes generate an immediate need for disposal, due to their susceptibility to rapid degradation, which calls for economic and logistic decisions. In fact, fishery wastes, unlike municipal wastes, have more proteins and other nitrogenous materials, responsible for rapid putrefaction (Venugopal & Sasidharan, 2021). The choice of a particular waste management option strongly depends on both the chemical composition and the mechanical properties of a datum residue. Typically, such biowastes are processed by paying (FAO, 2020) disposal costs to a third-party or specific waste management company.

The inadequate management of fish processing waste or by-products is one of the major problems that the fish industry faces nowadays. Traditionally, disposal of solid wastes encompasses dumping them into landfill, their use in silage, fishmeal, and fertilizer (without adequate treatment) or as a component of aqua- and poultry feeds (Venugopal & Sasidharan, 2021). These large quantities of fish by-product waste from fisheries would create serious pollution and disposal problems (Chalamaiah et al., 2012). For instance, the anaerobic decomposition of organic matter contained in fish leads to the breakdown of proteins and other nitrogenous compounds, releasing carbon dioxide, methane, amines, diamines, ammonia (NH₃) and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). In addition, there is an environmental concern associated with the disposal of fish wastes into ocean waters, including reduced oxygen levels in the seawaters at the ocean bottom; burial or smothering of living organisms; and introduction of disease or non-native and invasive species to the ecosystem of the sea floor (Venugopal & Sasidharan, 2021).

However, seafood non-edible residues contain a considerable number of biomolecules such as proteins, polysaccharides, lipids, carotenoids, vitamins, minerals, etc. Recovering these biomolecules can be an important way to improve global food security and mitigate environmental problems associated with seafood by-products/discards (Bruno et al., 2019). In this sense, biotechnological

processes offer an economic and versatile way to concentrate and transform resources from waste/wastewater into valuable products. The sustainable processing of biomass (food, feed, chemicals, materials) and bioenergy into a spectrum of marketable products and energy is called “biorefining” (Venugopal & Sasidharan, 2021). Considering fish and mollusc wastes as important sources of biomaterials and converting them into an economic opportunity for biorefineries and similar industries, represents a possible solution to overcome the problem of fish waste management and is in line with circular economy principles.

It is now estimated that up to 25-35% of the total volume of fishmeal and fish oil is produced using these by-products, but regional differences exist (FAO, 2020). A more sustainable option is to use them as a raw material for fertilizer production, avoiding the dispersion of nutrients that can turn into environmental pollutants. This process allows framing into circular economy (CE), which aims to reduce the usage of non-renewable raw materials and limits the quantity of generated waste. CE implementation in the fertilizer sector is recommended by both the European Union and the European Fertilizer Manufacturers Organization (Chojnacka et al., 2020). CE in the fertilizer industry in terms of material recycling in the form of implementation of alternative raw materials is aimed at the recovery of the biogenic elements: nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K). Nitrogen recovery (N-recovery) is achieved through the reuse of biomass (fresh or composted) and animal production wastes (manure, slurry) (Abubaker et al., 2015; Grigatti et al., 2019). All these materials carry a large amount of organic carbon and other elements essential for soil fertility or plant nutrition: sulfur, magnesium, calcium, and micronutrients (copper, manganese, zinc, and iron) (Chojnacka et al., 2020). Biochar production, which leads to the management of organic wastes, results in the recovery of organic carbon, which contains macronutrients and micronutrients (Usman et al., 2015). Biochar, also called bio-carbon, is obtained by pyrolyzing biomass under anoxic conditions (Zhang et al., 2020). Producing biochar from waste enables its reuse, which is in line with the goals of sustainable development. The selection of raw materials, process parameters and additives determine not only the functional properties of the biochar but also the economic efficiency and the scale of the environmental risk.

The main goal of this work is to valorise seafood by-products in terms of organic fertilizer or soil amendment. As it will be deepened later, this will be achieved by the pyrolysis and composting of the organic fraction of seafood by-products. By pyrolysis, it is possible to obtain biochar, which is further used in the composting of such materials. Biochar addition to the composting process shows the following benefits: **i)** improvement of physicochemical properties by adding more stable carbon; **ii)** increase of oxygen transfer to accelerate the decomposition of organic matter, **iii)** phytotoxicity reduction; **iv)** offsetting possible negative effects of compost in soils; and **v)** decrease of nitrogen losses and leachate volumes during composting (Guo et al., 2021; Oldfield et al., 2018a; Wang et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2017). The application of co-composted biochar (COMBI) on soil improves the soil organic carbon (SOC) pool that builds organic matter. This results in enhanced soil properties, including pH increase, soil sorption capacity responsible for water holding capacity and protection against nutrient leaching into deeper parts of the soil (Guo et al., 2021).

1.2. Context of the study

The work carried out in this master thesis is part of the Project "SEA2LAND - Producing advanced bio-based fertilizers from fisheries wastes", a 4-year collaborative Innovation Action (IA) funded by the EU in the frame of the Horizon 2020 program (101000402). The general objective of the project is to provide solutions to help overcome future challenges related to food production, climate change and waste reuse. Based on the circular economy model, this project aims to meet this challenge by improving and adapting technologies for nutrient recovery to produce bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) and Tailor-Made fertilizers (TMFs) from fishery and aquaculture by-products generated in Europe. In this way it contributes to independence and security in the supply of nutrients to European agricultural systems, mitigating the existing nutrient imbalance in Europe. In the long term, this will encourage the large-scale production of fertilizers in the EU from non-imported organic or secondary raw materials, on the side of the circular economy model, transforming by-products into nutrients for crops (<https://sea2landproject.eu/>).

The importance of this expected impact is clearer by knowing that the world's horticultural systems face a great balancing act between two needs: **(1)** raise the supply of food produced on the available farmland, since the global population will increase to more than 9.3 billion by 2050, and **(2)** reduce agriculture's impact on the environment and human health. Meeting these two targets presents a major sustainability challenge to scientists and producers (Colla et al., 2015). Therefore, with the rising demand to meet the nutritional requirements of a growing population and widespread consumer awareness of environmentally friendly agricultural practices as well as strict regulations on the use of chemical fertilizers, there is an urgent need to find alternative methods of sustainable horticultural production through technical and technological innovations. Composting is a sustainable technique that converts organic waste into a stable form of organic matter and fertilisers that can be used for agriculture as soil amendments.

1.2.1. Adriatic Sea Pilot Case in SEA2LAND project

The project proposes the implementation of 9 technologies in 7 demonstration pilots in 6 representative areas of the fishery sector (North, Baltic, Atlantic, Cantabrian, Mediterranean and Adriatic Seas). The role of UNIVPM in the Adriatic Sea Pilot Case is to develop a biorefinery fed by wastes from mollusc and fish processing industries. The goal of this refinery is to obtain protein hydrolysates for plant bio-stimulation, nitrogenous fertilizer, biochar-compost composite, and soil liming agent. From previous characterizations, as it will be described in Functional characterization of raw material, it was found that wastes from molluscs consist of around 20% of organic material (residual meat) and 80% of shells. Shells are mainly composed of inorganic material, and they are rich in CaCO_3 which will be used as a liming agent (to increase soil pH). The organic part, together with the fish wastes, is rich in proteins (more than 50% on a dry basis) and will be used to obtain:

- protein hydrolysates through enzymatic hydrolysis (out of the scope of this work);
- biochar-compost composite from the composting of solid residue from the hydrolysis step adding pyrolyzed leftovers (biochar).

To this purpose, mollusc and fish waste are recovered, respectively, from Co.Pe.Mo. (Cooperativa Pescatori Molluschicoltori) and Ittica del Conero Soc. Coop. Co.Pe.Mo. is considered as a point of reference for all Italian fishing cooperatives. They sell shellfish species from Marche Region such as mussels, clams, and murex. They produce around $500 \text{ t}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$ of mollusc by-products. Ittica del Conero Soc. Coop. has been operating for several years both in the marketing and processing of fish products

from the Adriatic Sea (tub gurnard, monkfish, hake, salmon, gilthead, cuttlefish, etc.) and disposes of around 80 tons of by-products (viscera, bones, heads, etc.) every year.

2. State of the art

2.1. Pyrolysis process

2.1.1. Process description

Pyrolysis is a thermochemical decomposition of biomass in absence of oxygen at a specified rate of temperature for a specified time. Pyrolysis of biomass is typically carried out in a relatively low-temperature range of 300 to 650 °C. During pyrolysis, large complex hydrocarbon molecules of biomass break down into relatively smaller and simpler molecules of gas, liquid, and char. The nature of its products depends on several factors, including pyrolysis temperature and heating rate. The initial product of pyrolysis is made of condensable gases and solid char. The condensable gas may break down further into non-condensable gases (CO, CO₂, H₂, and CH₄), liquid, and char (Figure 1). This decomposition occurs partially through gas-phase homogeneous reactions and partially through gas-solid phase heterogeneous thermal reactions. In gas-phase reactions, the condensable vapour is cracked into smaller molecules of non-condensable permanent gases such as CO and CO₂.

Figure 1: Pyrolysis process

The pyrolysis process could be divided into four stages:

- **Drying** (~100 °C): During the initial phase of biomass heating at low temperature, the free moisture and some loosely bound water are released. The free moisture evaporates, and the heat is then conducted into the biomass interior. If the humidity is high, the bound water aids the melting of the lignitic fraction, which solidifies on subsequent cooling.
- **Initial Stage** (100–300 °C): In this stage, exothermic dehydration of the biomass takes place with the release of water and low-molecular-weight gases like CO and CO₂.
- **Intermediate Stage** (>200 °C): This is primary pyrolysis, and it takes place in the temperature range of 200 to 600 °C. Most of the vapour or precursor to bio-oil is produced at this stage. Large molecules of biomass particles decompose into char (primary char), condensable gases (vapours and precursors of the liquid yield), and non-condensable gases.

- **Final stage** (~300–900 °C): The final stage of pyrolysis involves the secondary cracking of volatiles into char and non-condensable gases. If they reside in the biomass long enough, relatively large-molecular-weight condensable gases can crack, yielding additional char (called secondary char) and gases. This stage typically occurs above 300 °C: the condensable gases, if removed quickly from the reaction site, condense outside in the downstream reactor as tar or bio-oil.

From the decomposition of the initial biomass, three principal types of products are identified:

- **Solid**: mostly char; it is primarily carbon ($\cong 85\%$), but it can also contain some oxygen and hydrogen.
- **Liquid**: known as tar or bio-oil, is a black tarry fluid containing up to 20% water; it consists mainly of homologous phenolic compounds. The bio-oil is a mixture of complex hydrocarbons with large amounts of oxygen and water. This liquid phase is produced by rapidly and simultaneously depolymerizing and fragmenting the cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin components of biomass. The bio-oil is a microemulsion, in which the continuous phase is an aqueous solution of the products of cellulose and hemicellulose decomposition, and small molecules from lignin decomposition.
- **Gas**: it contains condensable (vapour) and non-condensable gases (primary gas). The vapours, which are made of heavier molecules, condense upon cooling, adding to the liquid yield of pyrolysis. The non-condensable gas mixture contains lower-molecular-weight gases like carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, and methane.

The product of pyrolysis depends on the design of the pyrolizer, the physical and chemical characteristics of the biomass, and important operating parameters such as:

- ~ **Heating rate**. Rapid heating yields higher volatiles and more reactive char than produced by a slower heating process; a slower heating rate and longer residence time result in secondary char produced from a reaction between the primary char and the volatiles.
- ~ **Final temperature (pyrolysis temperature)**. The pyrolysis temperature affects the composition, the yield of the product and the amount of char produced: low temperatures result in more char.
- ~ **Residence time in the reaction zone**. During slow heating, a slow or gradual removal of volatiles from the reactor permits a secondary reaction to occur between char particles and volatiles, leading to a secondary char formation.

Therefore, the operating parameters of a pyrolizer are adjusted to meet the requirement of the final product of interest (Basu, 2010). To maximize char production, a slow heating rate ($<0.01\text{--}2.0$ °C/s), low final temperature, and long gas residence time are required. To maximize liquid yield, a high heating rate, moderate final temperature (450–600 °C), and short gas residence time are required. To maximize gas production, a slow heating rate, high final temperature (700–900 °C), and long gas residence time are required. More in general, pyrolytic processes are commonly categorized into two main subclasses (Figure 2):

- **Slow pyrolysis**: it is the conventional type of pyrolysis which is characterized by a **slow heating rate and long residence time**. In slow pyrolysis, the biomass is pyrolyzed up to a temperature of

the order of 400–500 °C with a heating rate of about 0.1 to 1 °C/s for a time ranging between 5 - 30 min. Slow pyrolysis favours the formation of char, but liquid and gaseous products are also formed in small quantities. In addition, a lower heating rate and longer vapour residence time provide a suitable ambience and sufficient time for the secondary reactions to complete. Moreover, longer vapour residence time allows those vapours to be removed which are produced during the secondary reaction. This ultimately results in the formation of solid carbonaceous biochar.

- **Fast pyrolysis:** the biomass is heated up to a temperature of 850–1250 °C with a heating rate of 10–200 °C for a short period varying between 1 and 10 s. Fast pyrolysis is used to produce bio-oil as the oil product yield dominates the char and gaseous product yield. A typical fast pyrolysis produces 60–75% of liquid product, 15–25% of biochar and 10–20% of non-condensable gaseous products. The high heating rate involved in the fast pyrolysis converts the input biomass to the liquid product before it could react to form the char.

Figure 2: Pyrolysis classification

During pyrolysis, the degradation of the biomass takes place; some authors are studying the variation of the chemical composition of the biomass. The H/C and O/C of biomass can be estimated to be about 1.4–1.8 and 0.55–0.75, respectively, indicating that biomass is low aromaticity and owns high aliphatic content (Kim et al., 2012); some tests have been also done for fish biomass, resulting in very low H/C, almost 0.13-0.15. After pyrolysis, a significant decrease in the H/C and O/C atomic ratios was observed and it decreased straight with the pyrolysis temperature increasing (P. Fu et al., 2009). Below 500 °C, the decrease is mainly attributed to the dehydration, decarboxylation and decarbonylation of biomass into the water, CO₂, CO, etc. Above 500 °C, the H/C ratio decreases dramatically compared to the O/C ratio, which suggested direct dehydrogenation and demethanation of the chars occurred (P. Fu et al., 2009).

2.1.2. Suitable feedstocks

Biomass is complex organic or non-organic solid products derived from living or recently living organisms and available naturally. Various types of wastes such as animal manure, wastepaper, sludge and many industrial wastes are also treated as biomass because, like natural biomass, these waste materials also are a mixture of organic and non-organic compounds and can be processed to get energy.

Biomass can be classified in different ways, depending on its origin: some authors divide biomass into natural and anthropogenic: the first one has a natural origin, while the second one is formed by processing natural matter. Biomass can also be classified into five different groups depending on the source from where it is obtained (Vassilev et al., 2012):

- Woody: involves stem, branch, leaves, bark, lumps, and chips of different trees like pines, spruces and oaks.
- Agricultural: involves different crops, such as stalks, straw et, shells and different parts of various plants, flowers and grass.
- Aquatic: microalgae, plants, microbes, fungi and different kinds of water weeds.
- Human and animal waste: manure of different animals, cooked or uncooked food, fruits, paper, plastics and pulps. When these waste materials are treated and converted to useful energy products not only energy is being produced, but the problem of disposing of these materials also is reduced to a certain extent.
- Industrial waste biomass: waste from various industries like paper sludge from the paper industry, sugarcane residue from Sugar mills, waste from the food processing industry and others.

Animal and human waste biomass and industrial biomass are categorized differently because industrial biomass contains different types of toxic chemicals and harmful additives in it, while animal and human waste are free of these types of harmful exposures. The classification of biomass based on its sources can give an estimation of some of the elements present in it, useful to compare the energy content in biomass, which is highly important in the selection of biomass for pyrolysis.

Before the final thermal process, the raw materials are often pre-treated by physical (shredding, drying), chemical or biological (e.g., anaerobic digestion).

The choice of feedstock materials is important for obtaining the desired physicochemical properties of biochar. In particular, the content of basic elements (C, H, O, S) significantly affects the final properties, carbon participates in forming functional groups, hydrogen and oxygen, for the polarity and interactions with other compounds (Yaashikaa et al., 2020a).

Among many types of biomass, crop residues are the most commonly used feedstock materials for biochar production. Most of the agricultural biomass is lignocellulosic materials containing cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and inorganic ash at varying degrees. In addition, plant biomass is a beneficial energy source, mainly due to low nitrogen and sulphur content and relatively low CO₂ emissions. In general, biomass with high content of lignin tends to increase biochar yield because it is not completely decomposed in the typical pyrolytic temperature ranges, leading to higher fixed carbon content.

Animal waste is a material that needs to be managed. They consist of residues from animal husbandry (mainly manure, dead animals, and bedding) and slaughterhouse waste from meat processing, mostly bones (Azeem et al., 2021) and fishbones (Ren et al., 2021). Animal waste is a noxious material produced in huge quantities and is microbiologically hazardous and must be disposed of immediately. Bones and fish bones are natural bio composites, of which the organic part (proteins and fats) is the

carbon precursor, and the inorganic hydroxyapatite is the scaffold in the production of biochar (Ren et al., 2021).

Co-pyrolysis of two or more feedstocks bring about several favourable effects on the properties of the products: for example, co-pyrolysis of seafood waste and plant biomass increased the yield of H₂ by suppressing the formation of condensed hydrocarbons. In addition, the lignin content increases the yield property of biochar, such that it can be utilized as an amendment material to other lignin-deficient feedstock to enhance the yield of the produced biochar.

The use of lignocellulosic material and seafood waste together could be also justified by their chemical composition:

- The first was derived by the polymerization of cinnamic alcohol derivatives (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Lignin chemical composition - cinnamic alcohol (left) and lignin structure (right)

The presence of CH₃-O⁻ and CH₃-CO⁻ groups justifies the considerable quantities of methanol and acetic acid which are obtained from the dry distillation of wood: therefore, lignin is characterized by acid groups which can reduce its pH.

- The seafood waste contains mainly fats and proteins: the latter are composed of amino acids joined by an amide bond, called a peptide bond (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Formation of peptide bond

2.1.3. Product characteristics and use

Pyrolysis is an important conversion technology of biomass to produce biofuel and bio-chemicals, meanwhile, biochar is also the major product during biomass pyrolysis (Kan et al., 2016). Currently, how to use biochar has received increasing attention: firstly, biochar is defined as charcoal for soil amendment. Numerous researchers have proved that the potential biochar applications on soil amendment include carbon sequestration, soil fertility improvement, pollution remediation, and agricultural by-product/waste recycling (Gul & Whalen, 2016).

As mentioned before, the type of biochar production process and its conditions affect the quality of the product. Measurable quality parameters include elemental composition, ash content, bulk density,

porosity, surface functional groups or sorption properties. If biochar is used as amendment for the growth of consumable crops, it is essential to determine the pH or volatile compound content. If the material is applied to improve soil fertility or sequester carbon, it is necessary to assess the stability of the carbon or the rate of nutrients release (Saletnik et al., 2019).

The International Biochar Initiative (IBI) promotes industrial practices that use biochar according to environmental and ethical standards. According to the (IBI), organic carbon content is a critical parameter in assessing biochar quality. Biochar-based materials require **a min. 10% organic carbon content and an H/C_{org} ratio of less than 0.7** (as an indicator of biochar stability). The IBI standard involves the characterization of biochar for pH, total nitrogen content, CaCO₃ content, ash content, electrical conductivity and particle size distribution. An important aspect is the limited levels of some contaminants (heavy metals and organic metals) such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), etc. The type of raw material mainly influences the quality of biochar (processed or not) and the production process, which is associated with the emission of pollutants (e.g., ashes) (Meyer et al., 2017).

The European Biochar Certificate (EBC) was introduced to include biochar in fertilizers and soil conditioners regulation. This action was intended to reclassify biochar from waste to quality material and reassure customers and producers that the resulting biochar-based product meets quality standards and is safe to use. The quality of products following EBC requirements is confirmed by independent, accredited testing agencies (Meyer et al., 2017). The EBC document published guidelines related to the sustainable production of biochar, including quality parameters important for agricultural applications and their acceptable levels. (“Guidelines European Biochar Certificate for biochar production,” 2012).

Biochar quality control prevents the misuse of materials and the products that appear on the market meet certain standards, which protects consumers and the environment. Many modern techniques can be used to characterize the biochar and thus determine the quality class, including inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Brunauer Emmett Teller (BET) method, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) or scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Yaashikaa et al., 2020).

Figure 5: Biochar quality requirements relevant to agricultural applications

The addition of biochar into the soil can alter soil physical properties such as structure, pore size distribution, bulk density, and texture. This brings important implications for soil aeration, water holding capacity, plant growth, and soil workability (Manyà, 2012). Large pores are sites for the growth of symbiotic microorganisms: this property also improves the movement of water and air in soil layers, improving soil functionality and fertility (Shukla et al., 2021). By increasing the soil porosity and the number of extreme micropores, micropores and small pores, biochar significantly increases water retention and the stability of its aggregates also in sandy desert soil, thus increasing its resistance to wind erosion and desertification (G. Fu et al., 2021). However, the fact that the effect will not be the same in every type of soil should be considered. The positive effect of water retention is observed in sandy soil but in the case of soil rich in clay, the effect is the opposite - the conductivity of the water increases (Siedt et al., 2021).

It is reported that biochar application into the soil could increase the overall surface area of the soil (Chan et al., 2007) and consequently, could improve soil–water retention and soil aeration. The soil–water retention is determined by the distribution and connectivity of pores in the soil-matrix, which is largely regulated by soil particle size (texture), combined with structural characteristics (aggregation) and the soil organic matter (SOM) content. The soil aggregation can be improved by the addition of biochar, as a consequence of the related interactions with SOM, minerals, and polymers from micro activity, clay, and microbiological activity.

Certain studies have reported high cation exchange capacity (CEC) values for biochar (Yuan et al., 2011) (consistently higher than that of whole soil, clay, or soil organic matter), probably due to its negative surface charges. This can enable biochar to act as a binding agent. Nevertheless, the addition to a given soil of biochar with a high CEC does not necessarily imply an increase in the cation exchange capacity of the soil, which results in an enhancement of the ability of the soil to adsorb and retain cations (e.g., Mg_2^+ , Ca_2^+ , K^+ , and NH_4^+). The CEC of a given soil indicates how well some nutrients (cations) can be bound to the soil and, therefore, are available for plant uptake. An increase in nutrient retention also results in decreased leaching losses below the effective rooting zone: leaching of nutrients from soils decreases soil fertility, promotes soil acidification, and negatively affects the quality of surface and groundwater. In general, the incorporation of biochar into soil increased both pH and CEC. However, this improvement in soil quality was not observed for a high pH soil tested by Van Zwieten (Manyà, 2012).

Biochar can also be a source of nutrients for plants: their content depends mainly on the raw materials used and the conditions of the pyrolysis process. It can also be applied as a carrier of microorganisms, as well as to *remediate contaminated soils* and *reduce climate change* (Bolan et al., 2021).

Soil remediation

Due to the well-developed pore structure, various functional groups on the surface and high stability, which promotes the adsorption and degradation of various types of pollutants, biochar is predisposed to remediation of the soil environment (Shukla et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2022). Biochar has a high ability to adsorb pollutants, including complex inorganic and organic (aromatics, volatile organic compounds and fragrances) (Kamali et al., 2022a; Mailakeba & Rajashekhar Rao, 2021; C. Zhang et al., 2021). Literature reports that many organic and inorganic pollutants are removed by biochar directly and indirectly through the persistent free radicals (PFR) that it contains (Luo et al., 2021). Biochar is an efficient sorbent for polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs): it can reduce the content of PAHs in soil, depending on soil type, in particular on the content of organic matter (Kong et al., 2021). The bioaugmentation process based on an autochthonous bacterial consortium in combination with

biocarbon is more effective in the bioremediation of hydrocarbons than bioaugmentation alone (Guirado et al., 2021). Biochar modified with Fe–Mn oxide is a useful material for the remediation of soil contaminated with phthalates (Chang et al., 2021). Biochar-enriched soils have a greater ability to sorb pesticides: it reduces the bioavailability of pesticides, reducing their toxicity to soil organisms and limiting their potential leaching (Ogura et al., 2021). Biochar can be an effective material in the remediation of soil contaminated with organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) (Ali et al., 2019; Batool et al., 2022) and organophosphorus pesticides (OPPs) (Zhen et al., 2018). Some studies also showed that the addition of biochar to the soil contaminated with difenoconazole, metalaxyl, and thiophanate methyl can significantly reduce their bioavailability for plants (Kumar et al., 2017). The improvement in the ability to reduce pesticide concentrations after adding biochar to the soil is mainly due to the increased activity of microorganisms (Zhen et al., 2018).

The presence of various functional groups on the surface (e.g., carboxyl, hydroxyl, phenolic and carbonyl), high pH and cation exchange capacity are the functionalities of biochar useful to reduce the mobility or immobilization of heavy metals and nutrients (Kamali et al., 2022b; Ogura et al., 2021). It takes place through sorption processes, cation interactions, surface precipitation and surface complexation mechanisms. The increase in pH caused by the addition of basic biochar is one of the main factors reducing the mobility of metals (Mailakeba & Rajashekhar Rao, 2021). Research shows that the use of biochar reduces the toxicity of Pb(II), Cd(II) and Ni(II) by reducing their solubility and immobilizing them in more stable forms, making them less accessible to plants (Mailakeba & Rajashekhar Rao, 2021).

The effectiveness and speed of degradation of pollutants depend on many factors, such as raw materials used to obtain biochar and the pyrolysis temperature, which influence the sorption potential. In soil degradation studies, it was shown that the electrochemical properties of biochar and its surface area significantly influenced the speed of the remediation process. It has been shown that the appropriate treatment of biochar to increase redox capacity translates into its effectiveness in pesticide degradation (Chacón et al., 2022).

Reduction of GHGs emissions

Greenhouse gas emissions and related climate changes are one of the greatest problems of the modern world. Research on the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is carried out on many levels: one of the methods is to add into the soil biochar that was originally designed for capture and storage of carbon in the soil (Bolan et al., 2021; Matušík et al., 2022). During the biomass pyrolysis process, the relatively unstable C is transformed into its resistant form in biocarbon, thanks to which the carbon cycle is slower and enables carbon sequestration and CO₂ reduction. The efficiency of CO₂ adsorption is influenced by alkalinity, carbon content and minerals: the higher they are, the better the biochar will be able to capture CO₂. Its sorption takes place at the surface of the biochar due to van der Waals forces. The potential of biochar in carbon sequestration (C) is not the same for all types of agricultural soils, even when the same dose is applied. It has been shown that soil properties are the most important factor determining the degree of sequestration (Bi et al., 2020).

The addition of biochar can stimulate nitrifying and denitrifying bacteria and reduce N₂O emissions from soil (Gillingham et al., 2022) up to 50% by reducing the availability of mineral N by sorption and immobilization of N by microorganisms or inhibition of N₂O production (Lee et al., 2021). Ji et al. demonstrated the effect of biochar on reducing nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions from acidic soils in tea plantations by improving pH and increasing the number of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria. The effectiveness of the process is influenced by the types of biochar, soil properties, as well as chemical

forms and doses applied to the soil N (Lee et al., 2021). Nitrogen, carbon and the microbial community are substrates for major biochemical changes of soil nitrogen and carbon and are important factors influencing greenhouse gas emissions. The introduction of biochar to the soil, which contains activated organic carbon, which is a source of carbon for microorganisms, may increase CO₂ emissions. Yang et al. showed that in soil subjected to cyclical freezing and thawing, biochar increased carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions by almost 3.5% while increasing methane (CH₄) adsorption by over 2.5% and reducing nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions by over 35%.

Soil moisture and temperature were factors that significantly influenced the emissions (Yang et al., 2021). For biochar that is applied to soil, better economic and environmental benefits can be achieved by optimizing the C: N ratio (Xu et al., 2021). Some researches show that the addition of biochar to soil can be effective in mitigating climate change.

2.2. Composting process

Composting is the biological decomposition and stabilization of organic substrates, under conditions that allow the development of thermophilic temperatures as a result of the biologically produced heat, to produce a final product that is stable, free of pathogens and plant seeds, and can be beneficially applied to land. Thus, composting is a form of waste stabilization, but requires special conditions of moisture and aeration to produce thermophilic temperatures. The latter is generally considered to be above about 50°C. Maintenance of thermophilic temperatures is the primary mechanism for pathogen inactivation and seed destruction. Composting is usually applied to solid materials, making composting somewhat unique among the biological stabilization processes used in sanitary and biochemical engineering (Haug, 1993).

The composting process can be:

- **Aerobic:** is the decomposition of organic substrates in the presence of oxygen (air). The main products of biological metabolism are carbon dioxide, water, and heat.
- **Anaerobic:** is the biological decomposition of organic substrates in the absence of oxygen. Metabolic end products of anaerobic decomposition are methane, carbon dioxide, and numerous low molecular weight intermediates such as organic acids and alcohols.

Anaerobic composting releases significantly less energy per weight of organic decomposed compared to aerobic composting. Also, anaerobic composting has a higher odor potential because of the nature of many intermediate metabolites. For these reasons, almost all engineered compost systems are aerobic. Odor potential from compost is greatly reduced because organics that remain after proper composting are relatively stable with low rates of decomposition. The decomposition of substrate organics together with drying during composting can reduce the cost of subsequent handling and increase the attractiveness of compost for reuse. Organic composts can accomplish several beneficial purposes when applied to the land:

- compost can serve as a **source of organic matter** for maintaining or building supplies of soil humus, necessary for proper soil structure and moisture-holding capacity.
- compost can **improve the growth and vigor of crops** in commercial agriculture and home-related uses. Stable compost can reduce plant pathogens and improve plant resistance to diseases.
- compost **contains valuable nutrients** including nitrogen, phosphorus, and a variety of essential trace elements; the nutrient content of compost is related to the quality of the original organic substrate.

However, most composts are too low in nutrients to be classified as fertilizers; their main use is as a soil conditioner, mulch, top dressing, or organic base with fertilizer amendments. On the other hand, nutrients such as nitrogen are organically bound and slowly released throughout the growing season, making them less susceptible to be lost by leaching than soluble fertilizers (Haug, 1993).

Compost is also a proven organic supplement that can greatly improve crop yields and reduce irrigation requirements.

It is a good practice to add, together with the feedstocks, a bulking agent or amendment such as:

1. Structural or drying amendment: an organic or inorganic material added to reduce bulk density and increase air voids allowing for proper aeration.
2. Energy or fuel amendment: an organic material added to increase the quantity of biodegradable organics in the mixture and, thereby, increase the energy content of the mixture.

The ideal amendment is dry, has a low bulk density, and is relatively degradable. A bulking agent is a material, organic or inorganic, of sufficient size to provide structural support and maintain air spaces

within the composting matrix; bulking agents form a three-dimensional matrix of solid particles capable of self-support by particle-to-particle contacts.

The composting matrix is a network of solid particles that contain voids and interstices of varying size; voids between particles are filled with air, water, or a mixture of air and water:

- If the voids become completely filled with water, oxygen transfer is greatly restricted, and aerobic composting becomes impractical in the absence of constant agitation;
- if some water is removed and the voids fill with air, oxygen transfer begins, and aerobic composting is possible;
- If too much water is removed, however, microbial kinetics will be slowed by lack of moisture and the composting activity will decline.

The theoretically ideal moisture content approaches 100% because under such conditions biological decomposition occurs in the absence of any moisture limitation, but, under real conditions, the practical moisture content must be considerably <100% because it's applied to solid materials. Maintaining proper moisture and free airspace levels is a matter of balancing numerous competing forces. Moisture levels must be high enough to assure adequate rates of biological stabilization, yet not so high that free airspace (FAS) is eliminated, thus reducing the rate of oxygen transfer and in turn the rate of biological activity: **approximately 67% moisture and 30% FAS were found to be optimum conditions** (Haug, 1993) as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Effects of moisture and FAS on oxygen consumption rates of mixed samples

Conditioning of the feed substrates is important to the successful operation of the composting process. Feed conditioning is a process by which potential process limitations imposed by lack of moisture, free airspace, nutrients, or energy are selectively removed; three types of conditioning can be defined:

- physical or structural conditioning is defined as conditioning of the substrates to remove potential rate limitations caused by lack of moisture and/or free airspace. Moisture is essential to maintain microbial activity. Lack of moisture can impose severe rate limitations on the process; high content of water can reduce the energy needed to maintain the temperature in thermophilic conditions. Moisture content should generally be as high as possible without saturating the

substrate and removing all available free airspace. Free airspace (FAS) is important in maintaining aerobic conditions within a composting material; the optimum moisture contents fall in the range of FAS between about 20 and 35%.

- Chemical conditioning is defined as conditioning of the substrates to remove potential rate limitations caused by a lack of nutrients or other chemical imbalances.
- Thermodynamic conditioning is defined as conditioning of the feed mixture to assure that sufficient energy is available to drive the process.

Another important parameter to be monitored during the composting is the **air supply**:

- air must be supplied to satisfy the oxygen demand from organic decomposition (stoichiometric demand).
- air must be supplied to remove water from wet substrates to provide drying (drying demand). As air is heated by the composting material, it picks up moisture and thus dries the remaining material. Drying is an important benefit to be achieved during composting, particularly with wet substrates.
- air must be supplied to remove heat generated by organic decomposition to control temperatures (heat removal demand). If not controlled, process temperatures can reach such high levels that biological activity is impeded. The aeration rate can be used to control the rate of heat removal and thereby adjust the system temperature.

The request for oxygen can be estimated stoichiometrically, by knowing the general chemical composition of the feedstocks, showed in Table 1

Waste Component	Typical Chemical Composition	Reference
Carbohydrate	$(C_6H_{10}O_5)_x$	
Protein	$C_{16}H_{24}O_5N_4$	
Fat and Oil	$C_{50}H_{90}O_6$	
Sludge		
Primary	$C_{22}H_{39}O_{10}N$	
Combined	$C_{10}H_{19}O_3N$	McCarty ¹
Refuse (total organic fraction)	$C_{64}H_{104}O_{37}N$	Haug et al. ²
Wood	$C_{99}H_{146}O_{59}N$	Corey ³
Grass	$C_{295}H_{420}O_{186}N$	Corey ³
Garbage	$C_{23}H_{38}O_{17}N$	Corey ³
Food wastes	$C_{16}H_{27}O_8N$	Corey ³
Mixed paper	$C_{18}H_{26}O_{10}N$	Kayhanian and Tchobanoglous ⁴
Yard wastes	$C_{266}H_{434}O_{210}N$	Kayhanian and Tchobanoglous ⁴
Bacteria	$C_5H_7O_2N$	Kayhanian and Tchobanoglous ⁴
Fungi	$C_{10}H_{17}O_6N$	

Table 1: General chemical composition for the organic fraction of various organic materials

Oxygen is used for both oxidation of organic carbon and nitrification: the latter is responsible for the ammonia release; in general, the nitrification demand is much less than that required for organic oxidation. In addition, most of the produced ammonia will not be oxidized because part of it will be used directly for cell synthesis, but the largest fraction will be lost from the compost by volatilization. For this reason, the oxygen demand for nitrification generally is not considered when developing aeration demand for composting. **The typical values range from 1.2 – 2.0 g O₂/g BVS for most composting substrates** (Haug, 1993).

2.2.1. Existing evidence of biochar addition

In the last years, many studies are carried out to understand the effective improvement of soil properties with the addition of char.

(Chung et al., 2021) are studying the effect of biochar amendment on compost quality, gaseous emissions and pathogen reduction during in-vessel composting of chicken manure; composting is a process that converts organic waste into humus-like material with the help of microorganisms in an optimized environment (Chia et al., 2020; Sorathiya et al., 2014). However, traditional composting is a slow process, and in some cases, it results from the partial decomposition of materials. Immature compost possesses phytotoxic effects that can cause agricultural loss (Jeong et al., 2017). Additionally, certain pathogens can survive or regrow during composting, which may pose a threat to humans and the environment. To address the constraints of traditional composting, studies have suggested the implementation of composting with in-vessel composters for remediating livestock biowastes (Jeong et al., 2017). In-vessel composting is performed in a container or vessel that has a specialized internal structure and is attached to a turning mechanism and aeration device. This type of enclosed composting system provides a completely controlled environment that can help overcome several limitations inherent to conventional composting techniques; in-vessel composting does not require large areas. Besides, the productivity of in-vessel composting of manures is enhanced by the amendment of biochar which influences the productivity of the composting process by **enhancing microbial performance, altering physicochemical properties, enhancing substrate degradation, and resulting in rapid humification and gas emission**. Biochar is mostly alkaline due to the availability of extractable inorganic nutrients and its leads to pH increases, immobilized heavy metal activation, and subsequently decreased conductivity in the composted manure. The study of (Chung et al., 2021) found that chicken manure could be managed with a sufficient rate of biochar amendment with a **significant reduction in NH₃ emission**. Additionally, the in-vessel composting process produced nutrient-rich phytotoxic-free quality compost. The positive effects of chemical and microbiological changes with bacterial pathogenic contaminants removal were demonstrated by increasing the biochar ratio in the compost mixtures and, when **adding 10% of biochar**, the final compost can be used for improving soil fertility and crop production.

(Antonangelo et al., 2021) analysed the effect of the co-composted biochar (COMBI): this is made by adding the biochar at the beginning of the composting process. They understood that **there is higher benefits in using the co-composting end product COMBI than using the compost and biochar separately**. As a compost additive, biochar improves composting performance and humification process, enhances microbial diversity and activity, reduces greenhouse gas emissions, and immobilizes potentially toxic metals (PTMs) and organic pollutants associated with the compost (Guo et al., 2020). During the composting process, the temperature increases faster in the presence of biochar so does the duration of the thermophilic phase. As biochar does also enhance the water holding capacity (WHC), the desired moisture content of most composts in the range of 50–60% w/w is ensured when biochar is added at the beginning of the composting process (Godlewska et al., 2017). As a soil amendment, COMBI has been shown a great performance in improving soil properties and plant growth (Awasthi et al., 2017; Oldfield et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019), such as alleviating soil drought and salinity stresses (Lashari et al., 2015), immobilizing PTMs and organic pollutants (Rodríguez-Vila et al., 2016; Teodoro et al., 2020; Ye et al., 2019), and reducing their bioavailability to soil microorganisms and plants. Such positive results linked to COMBI application are even greater than the effects when simply mixing the final composting product with biochar, probably due to the

enhanced reactions of both products during the composting process. They look at the change of organic matter, nutrients and pollutants in biochar-amended compost:

- Organic matter

Dissolved organic carbon (DOC) was lower in biochar-amended compost than without biochar addition (J. Zhang et al., 2016). The lower DOC in the compost with biochar was partly due to improved aerobic microbial activities which were caused by enhanced aeration with biochar. In addition, has **higher stability than the compost without biochar** due to the formation of stabilized humic substances (containing fulvic and humic acids) during composting (Jindo et al., 2016).

- Macro plant nutrients

Composting with biochar typically showed **lower emission of NH₃ and a higher concentration of NO₃⁻** compared to that without biochar (Chen et al., 2010; Malińska et al., 2014). With biochar addition, the nitrification process where NH₃/NH₄⁺ is converted to NO₃⁻ by nitrifying bacteria was enhanced, while the ammonification process (the reverse route) was suppressed (López-Cano et al., 2016).

- Heavy metals

Heavy metal profiles in composting material depend on their origin. Sewage sludge and animal waste have shown higher levels of heavy metals than other organic wastes (Liu et al., 2017; Meng et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2018). Composting of sewage sludge and animal waste with biochar showed reduced mobility and bioavailability of heavy metals. It was shown that different temperatures used in biochar production determine biochar's ability for heavy metal immobilization. A study evaluated pyrolysis temperatures from 200 to 900°C, and the biochar produced at a temperature between 450 and 500°C showed better ability in Cu and Zn immobilization during biochar-amended composting (Li et al., 2014).

- Gaseous emissions

During composting, several major gaseous compounds such as methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and NH₃ can be emitted as the result of the degradation of organic matter (Chowdhury et al., 2014). Biochar addition to composting is beneficial in the **reduction of CH₄ emission** as compared to the case without biochar addition, which is due to the reduced bulk density, better aeration, and gas diffusion, creating growth conditions suitable for methanotrophs (consuming CH₄) while undesirable for methanogens (producing CH₄) (Vandecasteele et al., 2016). Reduced or less increased emission of N₂O was commonly reported on composting process enhancement with biochar (López-Cano et al., 2016; Vandecasteele et al., 2016). The main reasons are, firstly, biochar absorption of NO₃⁻ makes the substrate less available for denitrifying bacteria; secondly, metals such as iron and manganese bonded to biochar surface facilitate the chemical reduction of NO₃⁻ to N₂; thirdly, improved aeration condition facilitates nitrification while suppresses denitrification process.

The work of Antonangelo et al. (2021) showed that the addition of COMBI not only significantly increased the organic matter and nutrients of contaminated soil, but also improved its physical and chemical properties, such as electrical conductivity (EC) and pH. When grown with COMBI application, cereal crops (barley, maize, oat, quinoa, and wheat) showed a significant increase in grain yield of 39.7% in comparison to other treatments not receiving COMBI (Wang et al., 2019b). Lashari et al., (2015) also demonstrated significant improvement in soil properties, plant performance, and maize yield due to the use of COMBI on saline soil in China over two years, with potential increased benefits over time. Encouragingly, (Lu et al., 2015) found that the application of COMBI combined with pyroligneous acid increased the activities of urease and phosphatase enzymes in saline soils,

which alleviated salinity stress in plants. The authors combined COMBI and pyroligneous solution (PS) before their application and verified that both physical and chemical conditions of the salt-stressed soil were improved and thus increased wheat and maize production (Lashari et al., 2015) through a decline in soil salinity. (Schulz et al., 2013) showed that COMBI addition to sandy and loamy soil substrates led to increased plant growth with such effect enhanced as the rates of COMBI application increased. The authors attributed those findings to the increased total organic carbon (TOC) content in the soil, as it provides plant-available and mineralizable nutrients. In addition, (Oldfield et al., 2018).

confirmed that COMBI application was environmentally beneficial resulting in a cumulative lower environmental impact when compared to chemical fertilizers.

Liang et al (2021) had studied the benefits of the biochar-compost addition on *Phragmites australis* growth and, even in this case, they demonstrate that biochar addition can significantly improve the growth and physiology of *P. australis*, increase soil organic carbon (SOC) content and decrease soil $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content due to the N uptake by *P. australis*. Additionally, the mixture of biochar-compost had an enhanced effect compared to biochar alone on the growth of *P. australis* in saline soils.

2.3. Biochar and compost use in agriculture

The goal of the pyrolysis and subsequent composting processes is to produce a compost-like product that can act as soil improver or organic fertilizer. The final compost obtained in this study is coming from the processing of seafood waste and green waste, by adding char produced from the same waste stream. For this reason, the legislative framework related to production of both char and compost was taken into account:

- Regulation (EC) n. 1069/2009 of the European parliament and of the council of 21 October 2009, laying down health rules relating to animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption;
- Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European parliament and of the council of 5 June 2019, laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilizing products and repealing Regulation (EC) n. 2003/2003;
- Italian Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 "Riordino e revisione della disciplina in materia di fertilizzanti" and sequent modifications.

In particular, the EU 2019/1009 and D.Lgs. n. 75/2010 regulate the use and characteristic of biochar and compost in fertilizer formulation for following place BBFs on the market and application on agriculture.

Italian Legislative Decree n. 75/2010 defines different types of fertilizers:

- "organic fertiliser": a fertilizer derived from organic materials of animal or vegetable origin, consisting of organic compounds to which the main elements of fertility are chemically linked in organic form or in any case form an integral part of the matrix;
- "soil improvers": materials to be added to the soil in situ, mainly to preserve or improve its physical or chemical characteristics or biological activity, jointly or severally, the types and characteristics of which are listed in Annex 2.

According to the Italian Legislative Decree n. 75/2010, products listed in the relative Annexes, which use processed products of animal origin, may be placed on the market if the latter comply with the requirements and rules for processing laid down in Regulation (EC) No 1774/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council. The present regulation is abrogated by the Regulation (EC) n. 1069/2009, laying down health rules as regards animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption.

Regulation 1069/2009 aims to adequately control the risk, either by directing such products towards safe means of disposal or by using them for different purposes, provided that strict conditions are applied which minimize the health risks involved. The regulatory framework already indicates waste valorization, but it is not mandatory. Indeed, the manufacturing of organic fertilizers or soil improvers is specifically designed by Regulation 1069/2009 as an option for the Category 3 materials.

More specifically, Article 7 states that Animal by-products shall be categorized into specific categories which reflect the level of risk to public and animal health arising from those animal by-products. Raw material at the base of this study falls into **Category 3 material**, which can comprise the following animal by products:

- aquatic animals, and parts of such animals, except sea mammals, which did not show any signs of disease communicable to humans or animals;
- animal by-products from aquatic animals originating from establishments or plants manufacturing products for human consumption;

- material originating from animals which did not show any signs of disease communicable through that material to humans or animals, like shells from shellfish with soft tissue or flesh.

More in detail, this regulation states that Category 3 material shall be:

- processed, except in the case of material which has changed through decomposition or spoilage so as to present an unacceptable risk to public or animal health;
- used for the manufacturing of organic fertilizers or soil improvers, to be placed on the market in accordance with Article 32.

Article 32, providing rules for placing on the market and use, states that organic fertilizers and soil improvers may be placed on the market and used if:

- they are derived from Category 2 or Category 3 material;
- they have been produced in accordance with the conditions for pressure sterilization or with other conditions to prevent risks arising to public and animal health, in accordance with the requirements laid down pursuant to Article 15 and any measures which have been laid down in accordance with paragraph 3 of this Article;
- they come from approved or registered establishments or plants, as applicable; and
- in the case of meat-and-bone meal derived from Category 2 material and processed animal proteins intended to be used as or in organic fertilizers and soil improvers, they have been mixed with a component to exclude the subsequent use of the mixture for feeding purposes and marked when required by measures adopted under paragraph 3.

In the Annex 2 related to the soil improver, are defined the characteristics related to the final char produced after the pyrolysis process and the characteristics related to the final compost, as shown in the Table 4 and Table 5.

Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, instead, is focused on fertilizing products. It allows the use of biochar and ash-based products as fertilising products, pursuant to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. It must be ensured that the use of such fertilising products does not lead to general harmful effects on the environment or human health.

Also in this case, as in Legislative Decree 75/2010, the following are defined:

- nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium as "main macroelements",
- to calcium, magnesium, sodium and sulfur as "secondary macroelements".

Based on this distinction, the following are defined:

- "simple fertilizers" when they contain a single macro-element - main or secondary - or a single main macro-element in combination with one or more secondary macro-elements.
- "Composed fertilizers" when they contain more than one main macro-element - regardless of whether they also contain one or more secondary macro-elements - or do not contain any main macro-element but more than one secondary macro-element.

This regulation divides the origin of the final fertilizer into 14 categories of component materials (CMC); those of interest for this study are:

CMC 3 – compost: an EU fertilising product may contain compost obtained through aerobic composting exclusively of one or more of the following input materials:

- category 2 or 3 materials or related derivative products, in compliance with the conditions established by article 32, paragraphs 1 and 2, of regulation (EC) n. 1069/2009.
- composting additives necessary to improve process efficiency or the environmental performance of the composting process, provided that the total concentration of all additives does not exceed 5% of the total weight of the input material;

The compost must meet at least one of the following stability criteria:

a) oxygen absorption rate:

- definition: indicator of the degree of decomposition of biodegradable organic matter during a given period of time. The method is not suitable for material containing more than 20 % of particles of size > 10 mm;
- criterion: a maximum of 25 mmol O₂ /kg organic matter/h; or

b) self-heating factor:

- definition: maximum temperature reached by a compost under standard conditions, which is an indicator of the state of its aerobic biological activity;
- criterion: minimum Rottegrad III.

CMC 14 – an EU fertilising product may contain materials of pyrolysis or gasification obtained by thermochemical conversion, under conditions where oxygen is a limiting factor, of **Category 2** or **Category 3 materials** or their derived products (**Regulation (EC) n. 1069/2009**), alone or mixed with living or dead organisms or part of them.

The thermochemical conversion process must take place under conditions where oxygen is a limiting factor in order to reach a temperature of **at least 180 °C for at least two seconds in the reactor**. Pyrolysis and gasification materials shall have a molar ratio of hydrogen (H) to organic carbon (**H/C org**) of **less than 0,7** and tests shall be performed on the dry, **ashless fraction** for materials with a content of organic carbon (**C org**) **less than 50%**.

2.3.1. Biochar quality standards

The char produced by the pyrolysis process must meet certain quality standards in order to be used as a soil improver; two standards are available: IBI and EBC.

2.3.1.1. IBI (*International Biochar Initiative*)

IBI Biochar Standards document (IBI) is intended to establish a common definition for biochar, and standardized testing and measurement methods for selected physicochemical properties of biochar materials. These IBI Biochar Standards support not only baseline safety considerations but also the evolving understanding of the positive functions of biochar in soil. To qualify as biochar feedstock under these standards, the feedstock may be a combination of biomass and diluents but may not contain more than 2% by dry weight of contaminants (following Brinton 2000). Any diluents that constitute 10% or more by dry weight of the feedstock material must be reported as a feedstock component. Feedstocks are differentiated into two types: unprocessed feedstocks and processed feedstocks.

The IBI Biochar Standards do not prescribe production and handling parameters for biochar, but do include recommended best management practices (BMPs) for safe production and handling; in particular, this standard identifies three categories of test for the final char:

- **Test Category A** – Basic Utility Properties (required for all biochars): this set of tests measures the most basic properties required to assess the utility of a biochar material for use in soil, such as **physical properties** of particle size and moisture, as well as the **chemical properties** of elemental proportions [**Hydrogen (H), Carbon (C), and Nitrogen (N)**], **ash proportion**, Electrical Conductivity (EC) and **pH**. Organic carbon (C_{org}) content is used to assign the biochar material to one of three classes depending on the percentage of C_{org} in the material and representing the range of C_{org} contents typical of biochar materials. Carbon stability is indicated by the molar

ratio of hydrogen to organic carbon. Lower values of this ratio are correlated with greater carbon stability.

- **Test Category B** – Toxicant Assessment (required for all biochars): biochars made from processed feedstocks must be tested more frequently than biochars made from unprocessed feedstocks, as defined in Section 5 General Protocols and Restriction. Toxicants may be divided into two categories: those that may be present in the feedstocks used (metals and polychlorinated biphenyls), and those that may be produced by the thermochemical conversion process used to make biochar (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and dioxins/furans).
- **Test Category C** – Advanced Analysis and Soil Enhancement Properties (optional for all biochars): biochar may be tested for advanced analysis and enhancement properties in addition to meeting test requirements for Test Categories A and B; all tests in Test Category C, which include the volatile matter content and surface area of biochar, are optional.

IBI Standard is recommend to consider the molar H/C_{org} ratio to distinguish biochar from other thermochemically altered organic matter for several reasons:

1. H/C ratios change substantially with thermochemical treatment;
2. O/C ratios have been shown to correlate well with stability of biochars;
3. H/C and O/C ratios are closely related (for low-ash biochars <50% ash and <80% volatiles (ash-free basis));
4. H is determined directly in most laboratories, whereas O is calculated by subtraction.

The molar H/C_{org} ratio is a material property that is correlated with the degree of thermochemical alteration that produces fused aromatic ring structures in the material. The presence of these structures is an intrinsic measure of the stability of the material. As according to the EU 2019/1009, also IBI Standard use the upper H/C_{org} limit of 0.7: this value is set to distinguish biochar from biomass that has not been thermochemically altered and from other materials that have been only partially thermochemically altered. IBI Standard defines the term “thermochemically converted” to refer to thermochemically altered materials that have an H/C_{org} below 0.7: these materials have a greater proportion of fused aromatic ring structures.

2.3.1.2. EBC (European Biochar Certificate)

European Biochar Certificate (EBC) will enable and guarantee sustainable biochar production, processing and sale. It is introduced to provide customers with a reliable quality standard, while giving producers the opportunity to prove that their products meet well-defined and recognized quality standards. The goal of these guidelines is to encourage and ensure the control of biochar production and quality based on well-researched, legally backed-up, economically viable and practically applicable processes. Currently, the European Biochar Certificate is a voluntary industry standard in Europe; however, in Switzerland, it is obligatory for all biochar sold for use in agriculture. Several other countries aligned their biochar related regulations with the EBC.

European Biochar Certificate for sustainable production of biochar distinguishes the biochar in four different application classes, each with different threshold values and ecological requirements:

- EBC-Feed: meets all requirements of the EU feed regulation and may be used as feed or feed additive in animal husbandry;
- EBC-AgroOrganic and EBC-Agro: meet all requirements of the new, EU fertilizer regulations, so in this study these requirements are considered;

- **EBC-Material:** guarantees sustainably produced biochar, which can be used in industrial materials such as building materials, plastics, electronics, or textiles without risk to the environment and users.

To obtain the EBC certificate, the criteria given by EBC guideline must be met regarding the biomass used, the production technology, the properties of the biochar, occupational health and safety, and product labelling.

The biomass feedstock must have the following characteristics:

- Must be guaranteed the clean separation of non-organic substances such as metals, construction waste, electronic scrap, etc..
- To produce EBC-Feed, EBC-Agro, and EBC-AgroOrganic, the biomass used must not contain any paint residues, solvents or other potentially toxic impurities.
- For the production of EBC-Feed, EBC-Agro, and EBC-AgroOrganic, contamination of the biomass by plastic and rubber waste must be effectively and safely reduced to below 1% (m/m).

The guideline give indication also on the pyrolysis process, in particular the temperature must not change more than 20% during the production: for example, if a mixture of 50% cereal husks and 50% landscape conservation wood is pyrolyzed, the proportions may vary in the range 40% to 60% [$\pm(50\% \times 20\%) = \pm 10\%$]. In addition, to obtain the EBC certificate, the pyrolysis must be operated in an energy efficient manner, and the syngas produced during the process must be recovered or burned: in this way the environment impact is neutral, guaranteeing the production of climate positive biochar.

The biochar's organic carbon (Corg) content must be declared: it varies between about 35 % and 95 % of dry matter, depending on the biomass feedstock and the pyrolysis temperature. The molar **H/Corg ratio must be less than 0.7**: this ratio is an indicator of the degree of carbonisation and therefore of the biochar stability. The ratio is one of the most important characterising features of biochar and is indispensable for the determination of the C-sink value. Values fluctuate depending on the biomass and process used. Values exceeding 0.7 are an indication of non-pyrolytic chars or pyrolysis deficiencies.

The molar **O/Corg ratio must be less than 0.4**: it is also relevant for characterising biochar and differentiating it from other carbonisation products. Compared to the H/Corg ratio, direct measuring of the O content is expensive and not standardized. Therefore, the calculation of the O content from C, H, N, S and ash content is accepted.

Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) are determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA): during the pyrolysis process aromatic carbon, carbonates and a multitude of diverse volatile organic compounds are formed. The latter constitutes a large part of the pyrolysis gas that partially condensates on biochar surfaces and pores. These condensed pyrolysis gas compounds are substantial constituents of biochar materials, are essential for certain biochar functions and thus necessary for the characterisation of biochar.

The **biochar nutrient** contents must be declared at least regarding **nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium and calcium**: for the use in agriculture and animal husbandry nutrient information is legally required.

Threshold values for heavy metals are set, depending on the application class: for EBC-Agro, the maximum values for heavy metal contents are based on the German Federal Soil Protection Ordinance (BBodSchV); for EBC-AgroOrganic on the EU regulations for organic compost. During pyrolysis the weight of the original biomass is reduced by more than 50% due to the loss of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen, but not heavy metals leading to increased concentration. Heavy metal contents

beyond the limit values thus indicate above all the contamination of the biomass used and thus represent an additional control of the biomass quality. If the limit values for heavy metals for EBC material biochar are exceeded, the contaminated biochar thus contaminated must be disposed of as hazardous waste.

2.3.2. Requirements comparison

In this section are summarized the main differences related to the classification (Table 2), test methodology (Table 3) and requirements (Table 4 and Table 5) given by the frameworks and standards.

	D.Lgs. 75/2010	EU 2019/1009	EBC	IBI
Biochar	Soil improver n. 16	CMC 14	EBC- AgroOrganic EBC-Agro	-
Compost	Soil improver n. 5	CMC 3	-	-

Table 2: Classification products

	EBC	IBI
pH	DIN ISO 10390	04.11 TMECC (2001)
Moisture	DIN ISO 10390	ASTM D1762-84
C _{org}	calculation from CHN	ASTM D4373
Total ash	DIN 51719	ASTM D1762-84
Total Nitrogen	calculation from CHN	dry combustion-elemental analyzer following the same procedure for C _{tot}
Electrical conductivity	DIN ISO 11265	04.10 TMECC (2001)
CHN	DIN 51732	-
Oxygen (calculation)	DIN 51733	-
PAH	DIN EN 15527: 2008-9 (extraction with Toluol) DIN EN 16181: 2019-08 with extraction method 2	-
Metals	DIN 22022-2, DIN 22022-7, DIN EN ISO 17294-2 / DIN EN 1483:	US EPA 7000 (p27) US EPA 6010

Table 3: Test methodology comparison

	u.m.	D.Lgs. 75/2010	EU 1009/2019	EBC	IBI
Permitted feedstock	-	ok Category 3 CE 1069/2009	ok Category 3 CE 1069/2009	ok biomass	ok if no contaminant inside
H/C	-	≤0.7	<0.7	<0.7	<0.7
C _{org}	%	Class 1: ≥60%	7.5 - 50	<50	min 10%, max 60%
PAH	mg/kg DM	-	-	12	6 - 300
PCDDF	ng/kg	-	-	20	17
ndl-PCB	mg/kg dry	-	<0.8	0.2	0.2 -1
Cl	g/kg dry	-	<30	-	-
TI	mg/kg dry	-	<2	-	-
salinity	mS/m	≤1000	-	-	-
pH	-	tra 4 and 12	-	-	-
humidity	%	≥20	-	-	-

Table 4: Requirements comparison

Metal	u.m.	D.Lgs. 75/2010	EU 1009/2019	EBC	IBI
Cd	mg/kg dry	1.5	2	1.5	1.4 - 39
Hg	mg/kg dry	1.5	1	1	1
Ni	mg/kg dry	100	50	50	47 - 420
Pb	mg/kg dry	140	120	150	121 - 300
As	mg/kg dry	-	40	13	13 - 100
Cu	mg/kg dry	230	300	100	143 - 6000
Zn	mg/kg dry	500	800	400	416 - 7400

Table 5: Comparison of different requirements as metal concentration

3. Material & methods

This section describes the type and source of different raw materials used for the experimental activity of seafood waste valorisation. Different materials were first characterized to better target and design the following tests of pyrolysis and composting. Details on the set-up, procedure and control of the test are also provided in this section.

3.1. Raw materials

3.1.1. Source

3.1.1.1. Seafood by-products

The H2020 SEA2LAND Project focuses on the valorisation of seafood by-products as fertilizer. Therefore the experimental activity mainly dealt with mollusc and fish by-products, generated by Co.Pe.Mo. (Cooperativa Pescatori Molluschicoltori) and Ittica del Conero Soc.Coop., respectively. Both companies are located in Ancona Port (Marche Region – Italy).

The production activity of Co.Pe.Mo. is articulated through different steps: purification by washing, selection and sorting on special machines controlled by qualified personnel, and packaging. There are three production lines with annual productivity of 9830 tons of mollusc (year 2020). In particular, clams cover 79.5% of the total final product, followed by mussels (12.5%) and murex (8%). During the selection and sorting phase, there is a generation of by-products mainly composed of molluscs not suitable for the market since they are undersized, fouled with barnacles, broken shells or unwanted species (Figure 7).

Figure 7: By-products generation from the production stage of CO.PE.MO facility

Approximately 521 tons of shellfish by-products were produced in 2020, resulting in 5.30% of the total processed volume (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Marketing volume and by-products production of CO.PE.MO. Year 2020

Ittica del Conero Soc. Coop. is, instead, a smaller company which operates in the marketing and processing of fish products from the Adriatic Sea including tub gurnard, monkfish, hake, salmon, gilthead, cuttlefish, etc. It disposes of around 26 tons of by-products every year equivalent to 70 kg per day (Figure 9). Fish waste mainly consists of viscera, heads, bones, and every residue coming from the fish processing before being sold to restaurants, supermarkets or similar.

Figure 9: Monthly production of fish by-products from Ittica del Conero

As will be detailed in the results section, two main fractions are identified in the mollusc by-products (shell and residual meat). Since completely different in composition, mollusc waste management requires a first separation step to split the shell and the organic fraction. To chemical-physically characterize them, manual separation of around 1 kg of unprocessed sample was carried out. While at the process level, the mollusc waste was mixed with water and then reduced in size by using a shredding pump. Later on, heavier shells were separated from the lighter organic fraction by gravity (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Procedure of wet separation of mollusc waste

3.1.1.2. Green waste

As pointed out in *Suitable feedstocks*, pyrolysis is commonly used to valorize lignocellulosic biomasses which are not perfectly suitable for anaerobic digestion, for instance. Therefore, gardening waste was analysed and used as a benchmark for the evaluation of pyrolysis performance. Moreover, the addition of lignocellulosic substrate to seafood waste was investigated as a solution to improve char production and process sustainability.

On the other hand, gardening residues are also needed for composting process. Indeed, bulking agents are usually high-carbon materials such as shredded straw or cardboard, sawdust, wood chips or leaves which are mixed with the main substrate in order to create free air space in the compost pile, absorb water, and balance the C/N ratio.

For this reason, two gardening wastes were used in the experimental activity green waste kindly supplied by "La Gramigna srl" of Camerano (AN) and olive tree pruning. The first one, now on called "green waste", is more heterogenous because it originated from different gardening activities and so consists of wood debris and pruning, leaves, grass, and some soil residues. On the other hand, olive tree pruning waste, from now on called "pruning waste", is derived from the separate collection of a single gardening activity (olive tree pruning) and so is a more homogeneous material.

3.1.2. Functional characterization

Before being analysed, seafood by-products were dried at 80°C for 24h and ground with an impact mill, while gardening wastes were dried at 40°C for 24 h and ground with a Retsch mill with a 1 mm sieve.

All products were characterized in terms of chemical-physical composition to understand if they were suitable for the proposed valorisation route (pyrolysis and composting).

Apart from basic investigation such as humidity, volatile matter, lipid, nutrients and metals content, a thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was also performed to simulate the sample behaviour under pyrolysis conditions and quantify the fixed carbon of the material. Organic-rich substrate degrades if heated up to 500°C, while carbonates are stable at such temperature and show weight losses above 550°C.

TGA is a device able to measure the weight variation due to a gradual and controlled increase of temperature and controlled atmosphere (e.g. inert atmosphere if Nitrogen gas is fluxed during the analysis), therefore, the TGA allows a quantitative analysis of the composition of a sample, without however directly identifying the nature of the components.

The principle on which the TGA is based is that as the temperature increases, the material heats up and is therefore subjected to degradation since in the presence of heat, the molecules that make up

the matrix break up in the form of gas. During the test, nitrogen as gas carrier has been used in order to create an inert atmosphere in the reaction chamber, otherwise, if the test was performed under aerobic conditions, the combustion take place, generating oxidated gaseous compounds and producing only ashes as solid residue. The weight loss measured in TGA is therefore linked to the degradation processes.

TGA output consists of a thermograph in which the weight variation is reported over time (Figure 13) or temperature (Figure 12).

The micro-TGA consists of a precision scale in which two small crucibles are positioned inside: one crucible is filled with almost 20 mg of sample and a second empty crucible is used as reference. The scale continuously measures the weight variation of the sample due to its thermo-degradation.

Figure 11: Micro TGA

To simulate sample behaviour in pyrolysis conditions, the sample was heated from room temperature to 900°C in inert atmosphere with a heating rate of 10°C/min.

Because our aim is comparing the thermal behaviour of different samples, the drying step from room temperature to 150°C was not considered. The dried matter at 150°C has been considered as the initial mass. By increasing the temperature, it is possible to see a small part in which the weight is almost constant. "Thermal stability" is defined as the maximum temperature in which the biomass does not degrade in an inert atmosphere. Once this temperature is exceeded, it is possible to see a weight loss linked to the degradation of the organic part up to 550°C. At higher temperature, carbonates are also removed since the following equation takes place.

Calcium carbonate splits into a solid phase (CaO) and a gaseous part (CO₂) which is removed and quantified as weight loss.

The DTG (blue curve) represents the weight loss rate. When it's flat no weight losses are recorded, while the peak represents the temperature or the time (min or sec) in which weight loss is occurring at the maximum rate.

Figure 12: Example of thermograph under inert atmosphere, 10°C/min

The TGA (thermogravimetric analysis) should be also used to quantify the fixed carbon contained inside those raw materials: once the temperature of 900°C is reached, the nitrogen gas is switch into air. In this phase, the fixed carbon is removed because it's characterized by a pseudo-aromatic carbonaceous structure composed mainly of carbon which, at high temperature in air environment, is degraded; at the end only, inorganic ashes will remain inside the crucible. In Figure 13, fixed carbon determination is shown.

Figure 13: Example of fixed carbon determination (CF) from micro TGA: --- weight loss (TG) and --- temperatures (T)

To analyse more sample at the same time, macro TGA is used. It consists of a carousel with 20 stations in which the sample to be tested is placed, it is equipped with a weight scale which, once the

temperature is reached, begins to rotate, weighing the variation of each station and, once the mass is $< 0.02\%$ of the previous measurement, assume the mass constant. It was used to determine fixed carbon and ash content of biochar, as described in the 3.2.3.1. CHAR ANALYSIS.

Figure 14: TGA device

3.2. Pyrolysis lab-scale test

Once the raw materials have been characterized, it's possible to proceed with the pyrolysis process. For this experimental activity, fish waste and green waste were used. As shown in Figure 15, both wastes are first subjected to a grinding process to reduce the substrate size, then they are dried to reduce the water content as much as possible. Once the two materials have been pre-treated separately, it is possible to mix them considering different percentages to obtain the optimal mix, as will be explained in EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP. The substrate mix is then subjected to pyrolysis, where the combination between the absence of oxygen and the increase of temperature will degrade the organic part in two phases: a solid phase which remains inside the system (biochar) and a gaseous phase which enters into the condenser: the non-condensable phase remains in the form of syngas, while the condensable part becomes bio-oil.

Figure 15: Pyrolysis Workflow

3.2.1. REACTOR SET-UP

The slow pyrolysis was investigated by using the *PARR 4575 HP Pressure Reactor* (Figure 16).

On the upper part of PARR are installed:

1. a pressure gauge to monitor the pressure increase during the test,
2. the gas inlet valve to let the inert gas (N_2) enter the vessel,
3. the gas release valve which is then connected to the condenser.

From the gas inlet valve, the gas is going inside the head and thanks to the stirring shaft, the gas is spread inside the cylinder. Therefore, the reaction chamber is saturated with nitrogen and an inert atmosphere is created as required for pyrolyzing the sample. To avoid vacuum conditions inside the system, both valves (inlet and release) are closed during the test, since a negative pressure inside the vessel would favour the entry of external air, compromising the creation of an inert atmosphere by fluxing N_2 .

Figure 16: PARR - Configuration

The sample is put inside the metal vessel which is then fixed to the head using 8 screws. To increase thermal insulation and prevent air from entering the cylinder, a gasket is positioned between the vessel and the head.

To activate the pyrolytic process, the sample must be heated. Therefore, a mantle, which is equipped with electrical resistance, is positioned around the vessel. A thermocouple continuously measures the temperature reached by vessel "shell". Another thermocouple is, instead, installed on the head to monitor the real temperature value referred to the internal volume of the cylinder. The temperature difference between the shell and the head is about 150° C during the test because the vessel is 2 cm thick. For this reason, to have 400°C in the cylinder the shell temperature was set at 550°C.

During pyrolysis, a gas product is generated by the thermochemical conversion of initial biomass. This gas is composed of a condensable and a non-condensable fraction. The outlet gas system (Figure 18) consists of:

- I. **Gas release valve (6)** to regulate the output flow and allow the gas to escape.
- II. **Coil condenser** to separate the condensable from the non-condensable phase. Cold water circulation in the coil condenser ensures cooling and further condensation of condensable gases.
- III. **Glass flask** to collect the condensable fraction (bio-oil). The flask has two connections: one with the condenser to make the liquid fraction which has been cooled descend by gravity and the other with a pipe to collect the non-condensable gas.
- IV. **Gas bag** to collect the non-condensable fraction for further analysis.
- V. Silicon **pipes** for unit connection.

3.2.2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The system described in section 3.2.1 allows quantifying pyrolysis yields (%w/w of biochar, syngas and bio-oil) and recovering the three products for further qualitative analysis.

Eight pyrolysis tests were performed simulating **slow pyrolysis** conditions (maximum temperature of **400°C** and heating rate of **5.44 ± 0.38 °C/min**) to compare quantitatively and qualitatively the performances of pyrolyzing seafood waste. Wooden biomass (green waste) was set as the benchmark and its mixing with seafood waste was investigated.

The general procedure is synthetically described below:

- I. Weigh and place in the vessel a representative sample of biomass (around 20 g);
- II. Assemble the whole system as shown in Figure 17;
- III. Weigh the glass flask to have the value of the tare and assemble the cooling system;
- IV. Create an inert environment by blowing nitrogen for about 5 minutes inside the vessel (gas inlet valve open) so that the oxygen present inside the cylinder is removed;
- V. Once the inert environment is created, close the gas inlet and outlet valves to increase the gas residence time. Indeed, in this way, the gases produced during pyrolysis remain inside the vessel as long as possible;
- VI. Adjust the reaction temperature to 400°C by setting the mantle temperature at 550°C. The electrical resistance starts to heat the mantle (around 5.44 °C/min);
- VII. Control of vessel pressure by managing gas valves (in the following more details);
- VIII. Once the set temperature (400°C) is reached, maintain the system at 400°C for about 10 minutes to have enough time for the reaction to finish;
- IX. Disassemble the vessel the following day since the PARR is very hot;
- X. Analyse the syngas collected in the gas bag;
- XI. Extract the char, weigh it and then store it in a falcon probe for the following characterization;
- XII. Weigh the collected bio-oil.

Figure 17 PARR - Assembled system

During the tests, the heating time and the pressure inside the reactor were monitored. The latter gives an indication of the reactions taking place inside the reactor since the increase in pressure is associated with gas production. Any pressure increase is detected below 110°C; pressure starts to

increase above 110°C since at that temperature the moisture present in the sample evaporates. Above 180°C, it was possible to observe an increase in pressure due to the degradation of the organic substance present in the biomass. Whenever the PARR showed a maximum pressure of 1.6 psi, the release gas valve was opened to prevent safety issues. The condensation system is, indeed, constituted of glass components (condenser/bubbler) which is a brittle material and could break under high pressure. Furthermore, by opening the valves as little as possible, the residence time of the gas is increased leading to an increase in the yield of char production. Up to 390°C the gas generated by the biomass under investigation produced only non-condensable gas, while when this temperature was reached, the formation of oil was seen.

The chronological history of the test is reported below.

Data test	Type	FISH AMOUNT	GREEN AMOUNT	Pyrolysis conditions	
		%	%	Temperature [°C]	Heating time [min]
10/10/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	0.00	100.00	400	75
25/10/2022	100% fish waste	100.00	0.00	400	65
16/11/2022	50% fish - 50% urban green waste	50.00	50.00	400	70
18/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	0.00	100.00	400	73
22/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	0.00	100.00	400	83
06/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	30.00	70.00	400	68
12/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	30.00	70.00	400	69
15/12/2022	70% fish - 30% green waste	70.00	30.00	400	67

Table 6: Pyrolysis tests - chronological history

When test was carried out with 100% of fish waste, the oil tended to accumulate in the coil (Figure 18) because it was much more viscous than the bio-oil produced by green waste.

Figure 18: 1. Coil condenser; 2. Glass flask; 3. Full system with coil condenser

Therefore, for the following tests, the condenser was replaced by a bubbler (Figure 19). Using the coil condenser, the gas is cooled inside a coil, while in the bubbler there is a linear system that allows the oil to flow vertically. Since the gas in the condenser is cooled thanks to the water present inside the system, a basin was used for the bubbler where, having reached a temperature of about 250°C, cold water from the refrigerator was poured. This temperature was considered because at lower temperatures oil is surely not produced, but only water vapour and there is a partial degradation of the organic substance, i.e. the simpler molecules break up and become non-condensable gas. Also, some oil was lost as it remained within the system, so the collected oil is underreported by about a gram. Therefore, at the end of the test, the PARR outlet pipe was shortened since part of the oil condensed inside: to collect this product in order to obtain more precise mass balances, the PARR outlet valve was opened, the bag for collecting the non-condensable gas was detached from the system and the valve which connected the nitrogen cylinder was opened, so as to increase the pressure to make the condensed oil flow inside the bio-oil collecting flask. The bag was detached, otherwise the analysis of the collected gas resulted to be very diluted with nitrogen and, since the calculation of this dilution would not have been simple due to the variation of the blown flow, the problem was solved by detaching the bag.

Figure 19: Bubbler cooling system

When the condensation system doesn't work properly, there are also issue with biochar handling. The char is much tarrier, probably because part of the oil condenses directly inside the vessel and is unable to exit the system; to extract it. In such a case, it is necessary to scrape the char out of the vessel and the oil quantity is underestimated.

A further optimization of condensation system consists of shortening the outlet pipe (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Before and after shortening of outlet pipe

In Table 7 are summarized the feedstock ratio tested.

SEAFOOD AMOUNT %	GREEN WASTE AMOUNT %	N. TEST
0	100	3
30	70	2
50	50	1
70	30	1
100	0	1

Table 7: Pyrolysis test - feedstock ratios

3.2.3. PRODUCT YIELD DETERMINATION

The mass balance is very important to understand the performances of the reactor as mentioned in the previous chapter.

Some weighting procedures are needed before and after the pyrolysis test:

- Mass of initial sample (M_{in})
- Mass of final biochar $Mass_{char}$
- Mass of empty glass flask/blubber
- Mass of glass flask/blubber + collected bio-oil

In this way, biochar and bio-oil weight are directly measured.

Figure 21: Workflow of pyrolysis process

To play the mass balance, the first hypothesis is that the entire fractions remain inside the system, so there are not any kind of losses. So, the amount of syngas produced can be retrieve by difference.

$$Mass_{in} = Mass_{out}$$

Where the initial mass (M_{in}) is the sum of the mass of the fish waste and green waste:

$$Mass_{in} = Mass_{mix} = Mass_{fish\ waste} + Mass_{green\ waste}$$

On the other hand, the outlet mass (M_{out}) is the sum of the three fractions produced during the pyrolysis:

$$Mass_{out} = Mass_{char} + Mass_{bio-oil} + Mass_{syngas}$$

To complete the mass balance, the mass of syngas is finally calculated as:

$$Mass_{mix} = Mass_{char} + Mass_{bio-oil} + Mass_{syngas}$$

$$Mass_{syngas} = Mass_{mix} - Mass_{char} - Mass_{bio-oil}$$

Once the mass relating to the different fractions has been obtained, it is important to quantify the percentages of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contained within each fraction. As explained in the previous chapter 3.2.3, it is possible to quantify the percentages contained both in the char (using CHN) and in the syngas (using the analyser): the latter quantifies the percentages of CO₂, CO, H₂, N₂, O₂ and CH₄ contained within the gaseous product, therefore, considering the molecular weight of C, H and N, it is possible to calculate the percentage of these three elements. Since the bio-oil is only qualitatively characterized, its carbon content is retrieved by the difference between the two known fractions.

3.2.4. PRODUCTS CHARACTERIZATION

Qualitative and quantitative analyses were carried out on char, bio-oil and syngas to evaluate the influence of biomass source on the final product characteristics.

Moreover, biochar to be used in agriculture must comply with the European Regulation on Fertilizer (EU 2019/1009) and a quality assessment according to international standards (IBI and EBC) is recommended, but not mandatory, for such parameters not included in the legislation.

3.2.3.1. CHAR ANALYSIS

Once the vessel was dismantled, the char was extracted and stored inside a falcon probe to then play the following analysis for the characterization of the sample:

I. pH

According to the EBC (European Biochar Certificate) guideline, the procedure used is the DIN ISO 1390, in which it is take at least 5ml of air-dried char and put it into a glass vessel. Then add five times

the volume (25ml) of 0.01 M CaCl_2 solution and let's rotate for the suspension of the two matrices for 1h (Figure 22). At the end, the measure of the pH is done using a pH meter, which give us directly the measure (Figure 23).

Figure 22: pH measurement steps: 1. Char measurement; 2. Addition of CaCl_2 solution to char; 3. Rotation phase

Figure 23: 1. Storage of samples for pH measurement; 2. pH meter

II. Ash content (550°C) and fixed carbon

Also in this case, following the EBC guideline, the procedure is according to DIN 51719, which gives indications to how to determine the ash content: this is done using the TGA (thermogravimetric analysis).

For the measurement of the fixed carbon, once the temperature of 550°C is reached and the previous step is finished, the air is blown in, to know the value of the ashes, since what remains inside the carousel after the use of N_2 is fixed carbon and ash, so by the difference you can retrieve the value of fixed carbon.

III. CHN

According to the EBC guidelines, char to be used in agriculture must have specific optimal ratios, including H/C and O/Corg. Therefore, it's necessary to determine the percentage of Carbon,

Hydrogen and Nitrogen inside the char by using a CHN Analyzer (Figure 24). A weighed micro-sample is placed into the autoloader of the *TruSpec Micro* and is automatically dropped into the high-temperature combustion furnace, allowing the sample to combust. This combustion converts carbon to CO₂, hydrogen to H₂O, nitrogen to N₂, and sulfur to SO₂. The combustion gases are swept from the furnace, through scrubbing reagents, and onto the detection systems as they are released. Independent IR detectors are used for the simultaneous detection of carbon, hydrogen, and sulfur. Nitrogen is measured using a thermal conductivity detection system. The entire analysis cycle is completed in approximately 4 minutes.

Figure 24: CHN analyser

IV. Metals

For the determination of metals inside the char, it is necessary to follow the UNI EN 13650 procedure, which defines the method for the extraction of elements soluble in aqua regia, followed by analysis by optical spectroscopy. According to the regulations, for metals containing more than about 28% (m/m) organic matter, an additional treatment with nitric acid is required. In this regard, the dried sample (approximately 5 g) shall be ground to less than 500 µm in order to give a more homogeneous sample from which a sub-sample is taken and to increase the efficiency of acid attack by increasing the surface area of the particles. To do that, it's necessary to grind the sample using a mill until all the sub sample has passed through the sieve. After that, it's necessary to play the digestion: weight approximately 1 – 3 g of the finely ground test sample into the reactor vessel, moisten with about 0.5 – 1 ml of water and add, while mixing, 21 ml of hydrochloric acid (HCl - 12 mol/l; 37% mass/volume) followed by 7 ml of nitric acid (HNO₃ - not less than 65% mass/volume or 35ml of such acid diluted to one liter of water); allow to stand for 16 h at room temperature to allow for slow oxidation of the organic matter in the sample. then add a few roughened glass beads and place the reaction vessel on a cool heating apparatus, until reflux conditions are reached and maintain for 2h. After that, transfer the contents of the reaction vessel to a 100 ml volumetric flask allowing to stand so that most of any insoluble residue settles out of suspension and finally decant the relatively sediment-free supernatant onto a filter paper, discharging at least the first 10 ml of filtrate.

The determination of the extracted elements takes place using the *ICP-OES (Inductively Coupled Plasma – Optical Emission Spectroscopy)*: this is able to measure the light (optical emission) produced by a liquid sample when introduced into an argon gas plasma, inductively coupled. Through this mechanism it is possible to quantify the metals contained in the sample by measuring, for each one, the intensity of the light emitted with a specific optical bench (system of mirrors, lenses and gratings).

Figure 25: Emission spectrometer Varian ICP VISTA-MPX

The following elements were measured in char samples: Na, K, Mg, Ca and P defined as macroelements since present in a concentration greater than 2000 mg/kg, and Be, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Li, Mn, Mo, Ni, Pb, Sr, Ti, Tl, V and Zn as trace element since present in low concentration (below 400 mg/kg).

The basic instrument consists of the ICP torch where the plasma is generated and the sample nebulised in argon is introduced, and the optical part which collects and quantifies the light intensity emitted by the elements analysed.

3.2.3.2. BIO-OIL ANALYSIS

The bio-oil collected in the bubbler has been stored inside a small bottle. FT-IR analysis was carried out to qualitatively understand the oil composition using the *PerkinElmer Spectrum 100 Series spectrometer* (Figure 26) which is connected to a PC to control the instrument and manipulate the spectra collected.

Figure 26: Bio-oil analyzer

IR spectroscopy is an analytical technique based on the interaction between electromagnetic radiation and matter; infrared radiation, in general, refers to that part of the electromagnetic spectrum which lies between the visible and microwave regions: this area can be divided into near IR (13000 – 4000 cm^{-1}), medium IR (4000 – 200 cm^{-1}) and far (200 – 10 cm^{-1}). The area of interest for the study is between 4000 – 400 cm^{-1} , since it is the range in which the organic components are visible.

More precisely, this is vibration spectroscopy: when an organic molecule is hit by infrared radiation whose frequency (expressed in terms of wavenumbers, inversely proportional to the wavelength) is between 10,000 and 100 cm^{-1} , the energy released by the radiation itself is converted into vibrational energy, and there are two basic ways in which the molecule can vibrate:

- stretching vibration: due to rhythmic stretching along the bond axis;
- bending vibration: due to variation of the bond angle.

A stretching vibration, therefore, is a rhythmic movement along the bond axis resulting in an increase and decrease in the interatomic distance; a bending vibration, on the other hand, can be due to a change in the angle in the bonds with a common atom, or to a movement of a group of atoms with respect to the rest of the molecule without moving the atoms in the group, with respect to each other.

The IR spectrum, obtained by plotting the absorption intensity (which depends on the value of the dipole moment of the bond to which it refers) as a function of the wavelength, although it refers to the molecule in its entirety, is characterized by peaks referable to specific functional groups, forming part of its structure: it is precisely thanks to the reproducibility of these peaks, and above all of the characteristic absorption values, that it is possible to trace the structure of the molecule under examination.

The test was performed by first analyzing a tablet of sodium chloride because used as a reference value for subsequent tests. Indeed, to analyse the bio-oil it was necessary to place it on top of this tablet, as shown in Figure 27:

Figure 27: Bio-oil characterization - Sodium chloride tablet with bio-oil

After the analysis, the software shows a curve with various peaks (IR spectrum). Each peak corresponds to the interaction of the IR with a molecule, as will be explained in BIO-OIL CHARACTERIZATION; Figure 28 shows an example of IR spectra extracted by the software.

Figure 28: Example of IR spectra with band identification

The interpretation of such spectra is carried out by literature support (Hernández-Martínez et al., 2013).

3.2.3.3. SYNGAS ANALYSIS

The non-condensable gas was collected in a 2L gas bag to be further characterized with a portable analyzer "VARIO luxx".

Figure 29: Portable analyzer "VARIO luxx"

The Analyzer *VARIOluxx* is designed for the gas analysis of flue gases and provides a full set of all equipment and sensors required for an emission control measurement:

- heated probe incl. heated filter
- heated sample line
- gas conditioning unit including filters and gas cooler
- gas pump and flow control
- gas sensors
- sensors for temperature and flow measurement.

The analyzer draws a sample of the flue gases from the duct using a built-in gas pump; the probe is cleaned and dried using a gas cooler and built-in filter and analyses the extracted gas with

electrochemical and NDIR sensors. Draft and temperature are measured at the tip of the sampling probe.

Figure 30: Syngas analyzer – main features

The oxygen content of the sample gas is measured with 2 electrode electrochemical sensors, instead, the toxic gases like carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), Sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) are measured with 3 electrode sensors. The electrochemical sensors are based on gas diffusion technology, allowing the generation of the signal directly proportional and linear to the volume concentration (% or ppm) of the analysis gas components. When the gas being measured contacts the sensing electrode, it reacts on the electrode surface either through oxidation (for example CO, H₂S, SO₂, NO, H₂) or reduction (like NO₂, and Cl₂). The gas composition is displayed directly on the top of the device.

Additionally, from the syngas composition, it is possible to evaluate the calorific value of the mixture to be further valorised as an energy carrier. Each single gas component (CH₄, CO, CO₂, H₂ and O₂) has an intrinsic calorific value (Table 8) meaning that they are energy vectors which in standard conditions can produce energy. Since these compounds are in form of gas, it's necessary to consider the volume to calculate the calorific value. This step is very important because it allows us to calculate the energy that can subsequently be used to sustain the energy demand of the pyrolysis process.

HEATING POWER MJ/m ³				
CH ₄	CO	CO ₂	H ₂	O ₂
33.91	12.04	0	10.25	0

Table 8: Heating power (Source Engineering toolbox.com)

The quantity measured by the analyzer for each compound ($Concentration_{compound}$) was then converted into heating power according to:

$$Heating\ power_{compound} \left[\frac{MJ}{m^3} \right] = Heating\ value_{compound} * Concentration_{compound}$$

Since gas is a mix of these elements, to obtain the total calorific value it is therefore necessary to sum all the individual contributions:

$$Heating\ power_{total} = \sum_1^i Heating\ power_i$$

Where $i = CH_4, CO$ and H_2 .

3.3. Composting test

Co-composting of biochar and seafood waste is an alternative valorization route to recover bio-based fertilizer.

For this experimental activity, fish waste was used as main composting biomass, pruning waste as bulking agent and biochar as process improvement. Before starting the process, the raw materials are subjected to a first analysis to characterize the moisture and ash content inside them to obtain the optimal mix (EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP). As shown in Figure 31, all the substrates are mixed together to have the ultimate feedstock as much as possible homogeneous. The test starts with an active phase, where the microbial community is using the oxygen provided by an external blower to stabilize the substrate; in this phase thermophilic conditions are reached and the process is monitored controlling both air flow and temperature. At the same time, there could be leachate production and GHGs are released from the system. After that, the curing phase starts and stability analyses are performed to understand when compost is ready to be commercialized.

Figure 31: Block flow diagram of composting process

3.3.1. REACTOR SET-UP

Composting tests were carried out at forced aeration regime, in an adiabatic cylindrical reactor with an operating volume of 30 L. A perforated plate is fitted into the bottom of the reactor to support the material, help leachate removal and optimize the airflow circulation. Two orifices on the bottom aim to introduce air from a compressor and remove leachate, on the other side. Two more orifices are situated at the top cover to insert the temperature sensor and the other is used to remove the exhaust gases and then analyse oxygen concentration and gas emissions (GHG and NH_3). Data

acquisition and air flux are controlled by dedicated software. Schematic drawings are reported in Figure 32.

The working protocol of the composting pilot is summarised as follows. The steps to operate the pilot plant include:

1. **Switch on the mechanic and electronic devices:** switch on the air compressor, open the valve and regulate the relative pressure up to 3.5 bar. Switch on the laptop and the electrical panel.
2. **Remove the water content in the water traps.** Water traps are placed before oxygen and carbon dioxide sensors in order to condensate the water content of the outgoing gases and avoid any damage to the sensors.
3. Open the monitoring and controlling program.
4. **Check that all devices operate adequately.** Verify the oxygen and carbon dioxide sensors with the span gas. Test the communication between the monitoring and controlling software and the electronic devices (sensors, temperature probes and airflow meters and controllers).
5. **Preparation of the solid organic waste to treat:** mix the adequate ratio “fish waste/bulking agent” to provide enough Free Air Space (FAS) in the material and guarantee aerobic conditions. Mass ratio of 1:1 is used. Add biochar if required (0.1 kg per kg of fish waste)
6. **Insert the mixture inside the composter.** The mass of the waste inserted must be quantified.
7. Close the top cover of the reactor.
8. Insert the temperature probe in the corresponding hole of the top cover.
9. Connect the outgoing gases hole on the top cover to the sensors.
10. Close the leachate removal valve.
11. Connect the output of the airflow meter to the inlet point placed at the bottom of the reactor. The temperature probe monitors the temperature of the inlet airflow.
12. Start the monitoring and controlling software after **selecting the most appropriate airflow controller system.** Different controllers for airflow regulation have been implemented in the system: fixed flow rate or controlled by the oxygen content or temperature evolution.

1	Sloped base to facilitate leachate drainage	6	Outgoing gases
2	Perforate plate	7	Supporting structure
3	Insulated wall	8	Temperature probe location
4	Insulated cover	9	Leachate drainage valve
5	Inlet air valve		

Figure 32: Technical drawing of composting reactor

3.3.2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Three different tests were carried out, as shown in Table 9: the first and the second were performed in a bigger reactor considering at first the feedstock without biochar, and the second one with the addition of biochar coming from the pyrolysis of composted sludge. The first two tests are performed to see if the biochar can give some differences on the physical and chemical properties of the final product. In this project the third test is done in a smaller reactor (30 L) using the biochar produced under pyrolysis of pruning waste: it is not considered the obtained biochar from the **Pyrolysis lab-scale test** of green waste because the final amount was too low (order of grams).

Test	1*	2*	3
Reactor volume	100L	100L	30L
Substrate	fish waste	fish waste	fish waste
Bulking agent (BA)	pruning waste	pruning waste	pruning waste
Biochar	0	From composted sludge	From pruning waste
Substrate to BA ratio	1:1 kg:kg	1:1 kg:kg	1:1 kg:kg
Biochar addition	0	0.1 kg per kg of substrate	0.1 kg per kg of substrate
Aeration control	Time loop	Time loop	Oxygen/manual control
C/N	15	15	15
Initial humidity	40-60%	40-60%	40-60%
Initial target of FAS	60%	60%	60%

*: composting tests not performed in this work

Table 9: Compost tests

MONITORING

PROCESS PARAMETERS	Frequency	Device
Temperature (internal and external)	Online (every 10 mins)	2x PT100
Oxygen in exhausted gas	Online (every 10 mins)	
Leachate production	Every day	-
NH ₃ , VOC	Daily	MultiRAE
GHG	3 times per week	Bruel xxx
Mixture weight (weight losses)	Once per week	Scale
Biological stability of composting mixture	Once per week	OUR test, WTW
Humidity, VS of composting mixture	Once per week	

Table 10: Compost monitoring for test 3

3.3.3. GASEOUS EMISSIONS

Emission of pollutant gases is one of the main drawbacks of aerobic processes. The gaseous compounds emitted during composting might contribute to greenhouse effect (GHG emissions), eutrophication (for instance NH₃) or generation of particulate matter (for instance NH₃; or VOCs). Moreover, emission of odorous compounds (NH₃ and VOCs among others) might be partly responsible of complains from composting neighbourhoods, contributing to a lower social acceptance of the treatment plants.

Gaseous compounds of interest were monitored by taking daily gaseous samples during composting trials. Samples for their subsequent GHG (N₂O and CH₄) analysis were taken into Tedlar © bags, while NH₃, tVOCs and H₂S were measured in situ.

Because the composting reactor is hermetically closed, gas sampling of GHG was done directly from the outlet gas pipe after water traps. For odor emissions, analysis was directly done from the outlet gas pipe (before water trap) into a flux chamber that allowed the homogenisation and representativity of exhaust gases.

Total volatile organic compounds (tVOCs), NH₃ and H₂S concentration of the outlet gases of reactors were measured daily in situ with a MultiRAE Lite portable analyser (RAE Systems). Detailed characteristics of the sensors installed in the MultiRAE analyser are given in Table 11. Sometimes, in

particular during thermophilic stage, dilution of gas with environment air was required due to too high NH_3 emission rates which were over the detection limits of monitoring equipment.

Parameter	NH_3	tVOC	H_2S
Sensor type	Electrochemical sensor	10.6 Ev PID lamp	Electrochemical sensor
Detection range	100 ppm _v	0 – 1000 ppm _v isobutylene	0 – 100
Sensibility	1 ppm _v	1 ppm _v isobutylene	0.1 ppm _v

Table 11: Compost test - sensors characteristics for gas analysis

The gas sample contained inside the bag is instead analyzed using the *Brüel an Kjaer Multi-gas Monitor Type 1302*. This type of analysis is based on the ability of molecules to absorb energy in the form of infrared light and release it in the form of heat. The biogas sample is sucked into the device and sealed in an analysis cell while pulsating infrared light passes through an optical filter and then through the cell itself. The transmitted light is selectively absorbed by the gas sample to be analyzed and, as the light pulses, the gas temperature increases and then decreases, generating an acoustic signal. The acoustic signal, picked up by two microphones mounted inside the instrument, is proportional to the concentration of gas introduced. The machine described is therefore capable of analyzing 5 different types of gas in addition to any water vapor present, taking about two minutes to return the result in terms of concentration.

Figure 33: Bruel analyzer

In this study the values of particular interest are nitrogen dioxide (N_2O), methane (CH_4), carbon dioxide (CO_2), and water vapour. Each gas bag was analyzed twice.

3.3.4. PRODUCTS CHARACTERIZATION

At the beginning of the test (day zero) and every seven days, composting mixture was sampled and characterized. To take representative sample, reactor was emptied, biomass was mixed, sampled and as soon as possible put again in the reactor.

- I. **Moisture** was determined according to UNI EN 13040:2002, following this procedure:
- Put a crucible inside the oven at 105°C to remove the residual humidity contained inside it, until achieve constant weight;
 - Weigh the crucible (W_{Tare})
 - Place the sample inside the crucible and weigh (W_{Gross})
 - Calculated the initial weight of the sample ($W_{net} = W_{Gross} - W_{Tare}$)
 - Put the sample inside the hoven at 105°C for 12h in order to remove the moisture contained inside the sample
 - Weigh the sample at 105°C ($W_{105°C}$), calculated the moisture and the total solids (TS%):

$$Moisture \% = \frac{W_{gross} - W_{105°C}}{W_{gross} - W_{tare}} * 100$$

$$TS\% = 100 - Moisture \%$$

- Placed the sample inside the muffle at 550°C for one night in order to remove the volatile part;
- Weigh the sample in order to have $W_{550°C}$.

In this way, it's possible to calculate the the percentage of volatile and ashes into the total solids:

$$VS\%TS = \frac{W_{105°C} - W_{550°C}}{W_{105°C} - W_{tare}} * 100$$

$$Ash\%TS = 100 - VS\%TS$$

- II. **Biomass stability** was also monitored on raw material and along the test through UNI EN 16087-1 "Determination of biological activity - Oxygen Utilization Rate (OUR)", which is an indicator of the decomposition degree of the biodegradable organic matter in a certain period of time.

At first, it's necessary to prepare the sample:

- Break up lumps and pass the the sample through a 10 mm sieve;
- Determine the moisture content of the passing material according to EN 13040 and the organic matter per liter according to the following formula:

$$EOM(g) = \frac{20000}{W_{om} \times W_d}$$

Where

W_{om} is the organic matter content, in % mass of the dried sample according to EN 13039

W_d is the dry matter content, in % mass of the fresh sample according to EN 13040.

- Calculate the required mass of sample W_s to perform the test according to the following formula:

$$W_s(g) = EOM \cdot C_V$$

Where

C_V is the capacity of the vessel in liters.

- Place the calculated quantity of the sample in the clean reaction vessel;
- Add 180 ml of water, 10 ml of complete nutrient solution, 10 ml of pH buffer and 2.5 ml of nitrification inhibitor (allylthiourea);

- Place the sample on the mixing device (Figure 34) and start the mixing for 4 h to 8 h in the conditioned room (30±2)°C;

Figure 34: OUR measurement - mixing in conditioned room

- Measure the pH of the suspension: the value should be between 6.5 and 7.5, otherwise base (NaOH 0.5 mol) or acid (HCl 0.5 mol) should be added;
- Start the respiration measurement by filling the CO₂-absorbent containing unit with absorbent (such as NaOH-pellets, KOH-pellets or soda lime, which is a mixture of Ca(OH)₂, NaOH, KOH and water), start the shaking table and measure the pressure over seven days. The measurement ends after seven days, but can be ended if the pressure difference between the maximum and the minimum value is more than 10 kPa.
- Calculate the oxygen consumption according to the following formula:

$$O_c = \frac{\Delta P}{R(273.15 + T)} \times \frac{V_{gas} \cdot 10000}{W \cdot DM \cdot OM}$$

Where

O_c is the oxygen consumption [mmol O₂ per kg OM]

ΔP is the pressure drop in the headspace [kPa]

R is the gas constant (8.314 l kPa K⁻¹ mol⁻¹)

T is the temperature the measurement is performed [°C]

W is the initial mass of the sample [kg]

DM is the dry matter content of the sample [% mass]

OM is the organic matter content of the sample [% DM mass]

V_{gas} is the volume of the gas phase [ml]

$$V_{gas} = V_{vessel} - \frac{W \times DM \times 10000}{\rho} - \frac{W \times W_m \times 10000}{1000^*} - V_{liquid}$$

* taken as water density [kg m⁻³]

Where

V_{vessel} is the total volume of vessel [ml]

V_{liquid} all added liquids (water, nutrient solution, pH buffer and ATU solution) [ml]

W_m is the moisture content [% mass of fresh sample]

ρ is the calculated sample density [kg m⁻³]

$$\rho = \frac{1}{\frac{OM/100}{1550} + \frac{(100 - OM)/100}{2650}}$$

- Finally the oxygen uptake rate OUR is calculated:

$$OUR(\text{mmolO}_2 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{OM} \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}) = \frac{O_c}{\Delta T}$$

Where

ΔT is the time ΔP is taken [h].

Figure 35: OUR measurement - Beginning respiration (left) – end of the test (right)

- III. **Nitrogen content of the leachate** produced during the process and the compost at 7 and 15 days were determined by Kjeldahl method on dry matter. Basically, this method consists of three main steps (Figure 36):
 - digestion of the sample at high temperatures for 7 hours with strong sulfuric acid and mercury as catalysts, resulting in an ammonium sulphate solution;
 - distillation by adding a base to the ammonium sulphate solution to convert NH_4^+ to NH_3 , followed by boiling and condensation of the ammonia NH_3 gas in a receiving solution made of boric acid;
 - titration to quantify the amount of ammonia in the receiving solution.

Figure 36: TKN analysis - 1. Ammonium sulphate solution; 2. Distillation phase; 3. Titration phase

Thus, the amount of nitrogen in the sample can be calculated from the following relations respectively for solid and liquid samples:

$$TKN \left(\frac{gN}{kgTS} \right) = \frac{(A - B) * N * C}{W} , \text{ or } TKN \left(\frac{mgN}{l} \right) = \frac{(A - B) * N * C * 1000}{V}$$

Where:

- A is the ml of HCl solution used in titrating the sample,
- B is the ml of HCl solution used in titrating the blank,
- N is the normality of HCl solution,
- C is the milliequivalent weight to nitrogen (14 mg),
- W is the g of sample digested,
- V is the milliliters of sample digested.

4. Results

4.1. Functional characterization of raw material

4.1.1. Chemical-physical composition

The chemical-physical composition of seafood waste has been analyzed in order to assess the potential uses of raw materials and of the respective organic and inorganic fractions in the treatment scheme. For example, to be used as substrates in co-pyrolysis, seafood waste must contain a certain amount of organic content.

The two main components of the mollusc by-product (shell and residual meat) were manually separated from the overall by-products obtaining a meat yield for murex, clam, and mussel of 15.75%, 33% and 17.27% respectively. Fish waste did not require any separation step.

Figure 37: Seafood by-products (from left to right: clam, mussel and fish)

As expected, the shell has a low moisture content (<8%) and involves mainly inorganic compounds (>94% of ashes). On the other hand, the residual meat has only 19-28% of dry matter and the organic fraction represents between 74-89%. There is no significant difference between the three mollusc species (Table 12).

Fish waste in terms of humidity and organic (and inorganic) matter is very similar to the meat fraction of mollusc by-products (Table 12 and Figure 38).

Mollusc	By-product	DM	VS	Ash
		%	%DM	%DM
Clam	meat	24.60 ± 2.77	76.09 ± 8.21	23.91 ± 8.21
Murex	meat	28.16 ± 1.93	89.89 ± 4.39	10.11 ± 4.39
Mussel	meat	19.11 ± 1.23	74.14 ± 16.11	25.86 ± 16.11
Clam	shell	93.00 ± 3.04	3.94 ± .54	96.06 ± .54
Murex	shell	92.48 ± 3.91	5.93 ± 1.86	94.07 ± 1.86
Mussel	shell	93.65 ± 3.67	3.95 ± 2.05	96.05 ± 2.05
Mollusc Mix	all	65.13 ± 6.37	8.56 ± 1.64	91.44 ± 1.64
Fish Waste	all	26.16 ± 6.91	86.30 ± 4.45	13.70 ± 4.45

Table 12: Dry matter (DM), volatile solids (VS) and ashes in seafood by-products

Figure 38: Water, ashes and TVS in fish waste, mollusc meat and mollusc shell

Table 13 shows other physicochemical parameters like pH, salinity, chloride, and sulphate concentrations. The Cl⁻ concentration in the shell is 70-80% lower than in the residual meat but almost uniform between different mollusc species. Chlorides and sulphates content, being very soluble, could be affected by the intensity of the water washings. Similarly, the salinity, which is mainly correlated with the amount of washing carried out in the production line, shows around 90% reduction in the shell fraction. Again, fish waste has similar composition of mollusc meat even if showing lower salinity values.

Seafood	By-product	pH	Salinity	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻
		-	μS	%DM	%DM
Clam	organic	5.94 ± 0.42	10'449 ± 3'876	0.60 ± 0.07	1.96 ± 0.58
Murex	organic	6.74 ± 0.77	9'851 ± 6'434	0.46 ± 0.00	0.77 ± 0.04
Mussel	organic	5.75 ± 0.55	12'436 ± 2'558	0.56 ± 0.03	1.65 ± 0.19
Clam	shell	8.48 ± 0.09	733 ± 59	0.10 ± 0.01	Not analyzed
Murex	shell	8.71 ± 0.12	692 ± 122	0.12 ± 0.01	Not analyzed
Mussel	shell	8.54 ± 0.01	606 ± 145	0.12 ± 0.01	Not analyzed
Mollusc Mix	all	8.10 ± .57	5'572 ± 6'632	0.29 ± .01	Not analyzed
Fish Waste	all	5.96 ± 0.24	5342 ± 805	1.08 ± 0.23	0.41 ± 0.20

Table 13: pH, salinity, chloride, and sulphate in seafood by-products

Concerning nutrient content, as shown in Table 14, fish waste and residual meat of mollusc have the highest concentration of crude protein and phosphorous. On the other hand, all three shells contain low nitrogen (0.42 g N/kg of dry matter, on average) but are rich in calcium carbonate (>81.4% of CaCO₃ on a dry basis).

Seafood	By-product	P	Crude protein	Fats	CaCO ₃
		mg/kg DM	g/kg DM	g/kg DM	%DM
Clam	organic	9'195 ± 1'855	518 ± 76	227 ± 15	Not analyzed
Murex	organic	8'354 ± 2'395	643 ± 13	174 ± 82	Not analyzed
Mussel	organic	7'051 ± 1'912	497 ± 60	239 ± 51	Not analyzed
Clam	shell	368 ± 130	1.18 ± .34	Not analyzed	87.25 ± 3.87

Murex	shell	745 ± 229	2.57 ± 1.55	Not analyzed	81.42 ± 2.78
Mussel	shell	455 ± 177	4.14 ± .54	Not analyzed	87.40 ± 6.44
Mollusc mix	all	1'033 ± 305	7.35 ± 5.99	Not analyzed	79.42 ± 3.49
Fish waste	all	22'882 ± 10'640	442 ± 84	534 ± 67	Not analyzed

Table 14: Phosphorous, crude protein, total fat, and carbonate in the shellfish by-products

Other nutrients such as Na⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, and Ca²⁺ are also present in seafood waste (Table 15). Like for the previous parameters, the three species of mollusc waste are similar in composition. Fish waste are, instead, more comparable to residual meat.

Seafood	By-product	Na ⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺
Clam	organic	16'887 ± 3'035	2'924 ± 538	9'399 ± 3'341	47'780 ± 35'172
Murex	organic	11'195 ± 6'336	5'430 ± 1'908	9'715 ± 815	19'763 ± 12'718
Mussel	organic	13'699 ± 4'506	3'498 ± 1'598	9'324 ± 419	27'510 ± 17'664
Clam	shell	6'406 ± 1'290	323 ± 132	426 ± 179	349'409 ± 15'518
Murex	shell	5'812 ± 178	1'002 ± 281	662 ± 55	326'053 ± 11'122
Mussel	shell	4'016 ± 113	1'223 ± 83	197 ± 51	349'981 ± 25'787
Mollusc mix	all	5'997 ± 347	1'816 ± 598	970 ± 62	318'018 ± 13'978
Fish waste	all	8793 ± 383	3226 ± 485	7684 ± 850	7684 ± 850

Table 15: Sodium, Magnesium, Potassium and Calcium in the shellfish by-products

In particular, the main chemical characterization of samples used to carry out the following experimental activity (composting and pyrolysis test) are summarized in Table 16.

		PYROLYSIS TEST		COMPOSTING	
		FISH WASTE	GREEN WASTE	FISH WASTE	PRUNING WASTE
DM	%	17.60 ± 0.00	40.55 ± 3.32	24.19 ± 0.15	65.30 ± 5.23
ASH	%DM	xxx	21.56 ± 0.47	11.97 ± 0.49	4.99 ± 0.03
C	%DM	48.80 ± 0.00	33.20 ± 0.00	53.00 ± 0.00	47.80 ± 0.00
H	%DM	6.68 ± 0.00	5.65 ± 0.00	8.08 ± 0.00	6.31 ± 0.00
N	%DM	10.42 ± 0.00	1.43 ± 0.00	7.52 ± 0.00	1.70 ± 0.00

Table 16: Chemical characterization of raw materials

Pruning waste has a higher content of organic carbon than green waste because the first one is a selected waste, while the latter is very heterogeneous since it can also contain a fraction of land, so as the percentage of inorganic fraction increases. Green waste, therefore, can be considered a representative sample due to its heterogeneity, and for this reason it was selected as material to be pyrolyzed together with fish waste. As mentioned in Suitable feedstocks, Table 16 confirm that the main difference between fish waste and gardening waste is related to the dry matter content, mainly related to the chemical composition of the lignocellulose material, and the nitrogen content, since the fish waste contains proteins: this is an added value for the final product.

4.1.2. Thermograph spectra

For a rough evaluation of the most appropriate biomass to carry out the thermochemical process (pyrolysis), TGA on raw materials was performed and results are reported in the following section.

At first, the three species of mollusc by-products, collected from COPEMO separately, were pre-treated to remove shells from residual meat. TGAs on both manually and mechanically (by pump) separated shells of mussels, clams and murex were carried out.

As an example, Figure 39 reports thermograph from mussel shells analysis. In line with chemical-physical characterization, low weight losses were detected in 150-500°C range since low organic content is present on mollusc shells while high weight loss is produced around 700-800°C due to decarboxylation of calcium carbonate in calcium oxide ($\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$)

Figure 39: TGA results - Mussel shell separated manually & by pump

Moreover, TGA could be used for assessing performances of separation. After the separation process, recovered shells should show a reduction in organic matter compared to the not pre-treated sample. The comparison between manual and pump separation suggests that the first one is more efficient in mussels' sample while the second one is more efficient in murex and clam sample

(Figure 41). However, in any case the organic matter content remains too low for considering mollusc shell a suitable feedstock for pyrolysis.

Thermograph of not pre-treated mussel waste (shell + meat) shows similar results since, as pointed out in the previous section, shells account for around 80% of the total weight of mussel waste (Figure 40). In particular, a first loss of 13.2% by mass is located between 150 and 520°C (with a DTG peak at 301°C) attributable to the pyrolysis of the organic part, followed by a second loss with onset at 694°C and DTG peak at 747°C attributable to the decarboxylation of the calcium carbonate present in the sample. The analysis conducted entirely in an inert atmosphere (nitrogen) shows a final residue of 45.4% by mass attributable to fixed carbon and calcium oxide.

Figure 40. TGA results – not pre-treated mussel waste

The comparison between clams, mussels and murex with and without different processing is reported in Figure 41. Results confirm outcomes from chemical-physical characterization demonstrating that not relevant differences noticeable between mollusc species.

Figure 41: Pyrolyzable organic matter not pre-treated, separated by pump and manually

So, to increase pyrolysis sustainability, it is necessary to use another feedstock with higher organic content. One solution is to use fish by-products such as viscera. Heads, bones, whatever coming from fish processing before being sold to restaurant or supermarket. Thermograph of fish waste is shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: TGA results – Fish waste

The thermogravimetric curve shown in Figure 42 shows a first loss of 49.6% by mass with onset at 321°C and maximum rate of degradation at 355°C located between 150 and 390°C followed by a second loss of 22.9 % by mass between 390 and 570°C both attributable to the pyrolysis of organic material. The loss of 13.1% of mass between 570 and 900°C can be attributed to the decarboxylation of calcium carbonate. The transition from an inert atmosphere (nitrogen) to an oxidizing atmosphere (air) produces a loss of 8.7% by mass attributable to the combustion of fixed carbon (CF) with a final inorganic residue of 5.7% by mass. This lower inorganic content, in line with chemico-physical characterization, indicates suitability of fish waste for pyrolysis. On the other hand, it is worth mentioning that fish waste is quite wet material (around 20% of dry matter) so, energy for drying should be a drawback. More feasible should be the co-pyrolysis together with a lignocellulosic biomass, commonly used in thermochemical processes.

Also gardening waste were functionally characterized by TGA (Figure 43 and Figure 44).

Figure 43: Micro TGA - Green Waste

Figure 44: Micro TGA - Pruning Waste

The thermogravimetric curve shown in Figure 43 shows a residual moisture content of the sample equal to 16.4% in mass, a loss of 43.3% in mass with onset at 270°C and with DTG peaks (first derivative of the thermogravimetric profile) at 335°C and 479°C attributable to the pyrolysis of the organic part. At the end of the pyrolysis process there is a residue of 28.7% in mass; the transition from an inert atmosphere (nitrogen) to an oxidizing atmosphere (air) led to a further loss of 12.3% in mass attributable to the combustion of fixed carbon; the final residue of 16.4% in mass can be traced back to the inorganic residue.

By analyzing the thermogravimetric curve shown in Figure 44, it is possible to deduce a residual moisture content of the sample equal to 3.3% in mass, a loss of 57.9% in mass with onset at 258°C and with DTG peaks at 338 °C and 399°C attributable to the pyrolysis of the organic part. At the end of the pyrolysis process there is a residue of 20.2% in mass; the transition from an inert atmosphere (nitrogen) to an oxidizing atmosphere (air) led to a further loss of 18.2% in mass attributable to the combustion of fixed carbon; the final residue of 2.0% in mass can be traced back to the inorganic residue.

Sample		Loss 150-580 °C % dry	Total Loss % dry	Onset °C	Peak DTG °C	CF % dry
Green Waste	Test 1	51,8	80,4	270	335	14,7
	Test 2	50,9	81,6	262	338	13,5
Pruning Waste	Test 1	59,9	97,9	258	338	18,8
	Test 2	60,4	99,3	258	333	18,0
Fish Waste	Test 1	68,2	97,9	264	323	17,2
	Test 2	66,3	93,4	263	329	15,2

Table 17: Summary of micro TGA tests

Figure 45: Comparison of weight loss up to 580°C, ash and fixed carbon content for Urban Green Waste sample - GRAMIGNA, Pruning Waste, Fish Waste

From the results shown in Figure 45 it is evident that fish waste is the sample with the highest content of organic material (Weight loss % 580°C). Despite this, the pruning waste turns out to be the best candidate for the pyrolysis process given the greater quantity of fixed carbon at the end of the nitrogen step at 900°C, probably because it is a selected product containing a greater quantity of lignin.

A combination of gardening waste (pruning waste) and seafood waste was characterized through micro TGA to evaluate their behavior.

In particular, fish waste was mixed with mollusc meat in 1: mass ratio (on wet basis), as expected from SEA2LAND biorefinery concept, and was combined with pruning waste at different ratio before being analysed through TGA.

Figure 46: TGA results - pruning waste + seafood waste

Linear relationship was found between the feedstock characteristics and the amount of seafood in the mixture (Figure 46). The lower the amount of seafood waste, the higher was the organic carbon and fixed carbon and, consequently, the lower amount of ashes. Indeed the seafood waste used in the test show a relevant inorganic fraction, probably due to an inappropriate separation step Table 17. When the amount of seafood waste was higher, there was an increase of the content related to the shells inside that material, which is mainly composed by carbonates, so inorganic part, disfavoring the fixed carbon amount inside the char. As mentioned in the Green waste chapter, the presence of lignocellulose material will favor the char yield related to the higher organic content, for this reason the pyrolysis test is performed considering both green waste and seafood waste.

4.2. Pyrolysis performances

This chapter describes the pyrolysis tests and the results coming from the analysis of the products.

4.2.1. PRODUCT YIELD

The first test with the green waste resulted in 5.4 g of biochar, 0.7 g of bio-oil and 8 g of syngas corresponding to the 38.3%, 5% and 56.7% of initial biomass. The collected oil was not very viscous, almost watery (Figure 47 left), probably because the green waste is low in fat. Biochar was very dusty (Figure 47 right), so no problems were encountered in extracting it from the vessel.

Figure 47: 1 and 2. Bio-oil 100% GW (1st test); 3. Char 100% GW (1st test)

The second test was carried out with 100% seafood waste, in order to have the characterization of the char produced exclusively from this material. As mentioned in the Suitable feedstocks, the organic material needs a lignocellulosic fraction in order to increase the char yield. In any case, this test was performed with a view to finding the right proportions between green waste and seafood waste. Compared to the first test, less char was produced (26.9%), confirming the studies found in the literature (Suitable feedstocks), and more oil (34.7%), justifiable by the fact that the fish is made up of a fat part. It is worth mentioning that actually the amount of measured oil at the end of the test was underestimated due to inefficiency of the condensation system (EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP).

Figure 48: Pyrolysis test - 100% seafood waste - char & bio-oil

The third trials consisted of pyrolysis of 50-50 mix of green and fish waste. 7.3 g of char (36.5%), 7.7 g of bio-oil (38.5%) and 5 g of syngas (25 %) were obtained. Comparing the percentage of char produced in the first three tests, it was possible to observe how the lignocellulosic fraction has a great influence on the amount of solid produced, since 38.3% of char was extracted in the first test (100% green waste). Furthermore, the char was less dusty and more compact than that produced

in the first test, this denotes how the lignocellulosic fraction greatly influenced the physical and chemical characteristics of the char. Furthermore, the presence of hydrogen was detected resulting in a greater heating power than in the first two tests performed.

Figure 49: Pyrolysis test – 50% green waste 50% seafood waste – char

Since the difference in the percentage of char produced between the first and third tests was not significant, and the presence of hydrogen was seen in the syngas only in the test performed by mixing the two substrates, it was decided to repeat the test again using only the green waste. The fourth test produced significantly different quantities than the first one, generating 8.2 g of char (41%), 3.9 g of bio-oil (19.5%) and 7.9 g of syngas (39.5%). It was thought that the greatest influence was given by the extraction of the oil from the system. Therefore, the output system was further optimized by decreasing the length of the pipes. Furthermore, differently from the first test, a small percentage of hydrogen was detected in the syngas. Thus, a third test with 100% green waste was carried out to evaluate replicability. Indeed, the initial biomass yielded in 40% of char, 23.3% of oil and the remaining syngas had a very similar composition to the fourth test (Table 18).

Figure 50: Pyrolysis test – 100% green waste – bio-oil

Pyrolysis of 70% green waste and 30% seafood produced 35.9% of char, 16% of bio-oil and 48.1% of syngas. This high percentage of syngas indicates that the pyrolyzed biomass has a high content of volatile organic matter, and by analyzing the syngas, it is possible to understand the calorific value of this product. Both the char and the bio-oil looked very similar to those of the test performed with only green waste: the oil was watery, much less dense than the seafood bio-oil. The test was repeated again for the problems described in the EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP, producing almost the same quantities of char but higher amount of oil. These differences may also derive from the heterogeneity of the Green waste sample. In any case, the quantities do not differ much each other, even if the seventh test is more representative because, comparing the percentages of char and bio-oil with the fifth test (100% green waste) and the second (100% seafood), the percentages are consistent with the literature.

Finally, the last test was performed with 30% green waste and 70% seafood waste, as explained in EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP, generating 36.7% char, 38% oil and 25.3% syngas. This test confirmed the replicability of the previous tests because as the quantity of seafood waste increases, a greater quantity of oil produced is expected, while by increasing the percentage of green waste in the initial sample, there is an increase in the char generated during pyrolysis (Figure 51).

Table 18 shows the summary of the eight pyrolysis tests performed:

SEAFOOD WASTE	GREEN WASTE	Initial weight [g]		Solid residue	Oil	Total syngas
		Green waste	Seafood waste	%	%	%
0	100	14.1	0	38.3	5	56.7
100	0	0	21.6	26.9	34.7	38.4
50	50	10	10	36.5	38.5	25
0	100	20	0	41	19.5	39.5
0	100	15	0	40	23.3	36.7
30	70	10.5	4.5	35.9	16	48.1
30	70	10.5	4.5	38	22	40
70	30	4.5	10.5	36.7	38	25.3

Table 18: Pyrolysis tests summary

Figure 51: Pyrolysis results - biochar & bio-oil yields

4.2.2. BIOCHAR CHARACTERIZATION

Once the char was extracted from the vessel and weighed (43), it was characterized as described in section 3.2.3.1. CHAR ANALYSIS and compared to existing standard and regulations (Biochar and compost use in agriculture).

SEAFOOD WASTE AMOUNT	GREEN WASTE AMOUNT	pH
%	%	-
0	100	9.34 ± 0.48
30	70	10.81 ± 0.26
50	50	10.10
70	30	10.78
100	0	9.17 ± 0.42

Table 19: Char characterization - pH results

The pH of obtained char (Table 19) can be influenced by two factors: the ash content mainly made up of carbonates and basic oxides, which tends to increase the pH, and the organic content where hydroxyl groups bonded to the aromatic rings are present (decrease the pH). Anyway, the values obtained from the pH analysis are similar along the different biomass ratio. As expected, all biochar sample are basic (pH greater than 7) and the addition of green waste biomass to the seafood waste feedstock is not influencing pH;

According to the procedure 48, the fixed carbon and the ash at 550°C are derived from TGA analysis. Precision scale continuously measures the weight of the sample, so it is possible to extract the trend of the weight residue of the sample, as shown in the following graphs:

Figure 52: TGA results – 100% green waste

Comparing the first three graphs extrapolated from the analysis performed on 100% GW samples, it is possible to notice how the trends are very similar to each other, therefore the tests have good replicability. Another important aspect is the decrease of the weight residue with the simultaneous increase of temperature; it's possible to distinguish three parts of the curves:

- the first one (up to 150°C) in which the moisture content of the char is removed;

- the second linear part (between 250°C – 900°C) in which the volatilization of the organic part bound to the aliphatic chain inside the char takes place;
- the final part in which there is the switch from nitrogen to aerated environment, where the decomposition of the fixed carbon take place.

Figure 53: TGA results – 100% seafood waste

Differently from the behaviour seen in the 100% green waste sample, the char coming from the pyrolysis of 100% seafood waste shows an initial part where there is not a weight loss and, after that, there is an almost constant trend of weight residue inside the device starting from 600°C. The main difference is linked to the final part of the curve before the plateau, in which the TGA switch the nitrogen into air, so is indicating the fixed carbon.

Figure 54: TGA results – 50% seafood waste 50% green waste

CHAR 06.12.22 - 30% Seafood Waste 70% GW

CHAR 12.12.22 - 30% Seafood Waste 70% GW

Trends of the TGA analysis using the char coming from the pyrolysis with 30% seafood waste and 70% green waste are the same: this is an indication of good replicability of all the tests.

CHAR 15.12.22 - 70% Seafood Waste 30% GW

Data test	Type	Fixed Carbon	Ash 550°
		[%]	[%]
10/10/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	16.5	39.135
25/10/2022	100% fish waste	16.3	41.83
16/11/2022	50% fish - 50% urban green waste	14	42.35
18/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	13	40.98
22/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	7.7	37.41
06/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	6.2	44.17
12/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	13.9	48.11
15/12/2022	70% fish - 30% green waste	12	43.72

Table 20: TGA results - fixed carbon & ashes

Table 20 shows the results obtained by analyzing the sample following the procedure 48: considering the fixed carbon, pyrolysing the same substrate, a difference of about 7% is found, probably because, as mentioned in Source chapter, the samples are heterogeneous, so the presence of soil influences the quantity of organic substance and therefore the final value of fixed carbon.

This difference is less pronounced in the ash analysis at 550°C, as shown in Figure 55.

Figure 55: Trend of Seafood waste amount vs ash

The trend related to the ash content (Figure 55) is almost constant because the degradation of the organic content, lead to the ash formation, made up mainly by inorganic materials, so, at the end of the TGA test, the percentage of those materials is pretty similar.

From these two tests it is possible to see that the addition of seafood waste to the green waste does not particularly affect the pH, ashes content and fixed carbon of the char.

Table 21 report the results coming from the analysis of CHN (48):

Data test	Type	C	H	N
		[%]	[%]	[%]
10/10/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	49.2	2.89	1.44
25/10/2022	100% fish waste	44.8	2.41	6.44
16/11/2022	50% fish - 50% urban green waste	38.4	2.27	3.98
18/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	37.8	2.23	1.28
22/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	44.6	2.39	1.46
06/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	43.9	2.28	3.56
12/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	45	2.38	3.1
15/12/2022	70% fish - 30% green waste	44	2.62	5.24

Table 21: CHN results

This first analysis gives an indication of the carbon present inside the char, which derives from the type of biomass pyrolyzed. These values are not very different each other (Figure 56 and Figure 57); more evident difference is related to the nitrogen content: the higher is the amount of seafood waste into the initial sample, the higher will be the nitrogen amount inside the char (Figure 58) since fish waste is a protein-rich biomass as also outlined from CHN results of the raw materials (Table 16). It is a positive outcome since biochar is intended to work as additive in composting and so be later on used in agricultural. Therefore, the nitrogen content of fish waste is preserved in the biochar and available for fertilizing or amending the soil.

Figure 56: Carbon content vs Seafood waste amount

Figure 57: Hydrogen content vs Seafood waste amount

Figure 58: Nitrogen content vs Seafood waste amount

The CHN test is very important especially because allows having values to then calculate the ratio H/C, which is an important requirement according to the international standards (Biochar quality standards) since gives an indication of biochar stability.

Data test	Type	H/C
	STANDARD LIMIT	
10/10/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	0.05874
25/10/2022	100% fish waste	0.05379
16/11/2022	50% fish - 50% urban green waste	0.05911
18/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	0.05899
22/11/2022	100% urban green waste Camerano	0.05359
06/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	0.05194
12/12/2022	30% fish - 70% green waste	0.05289
15/12/2022	70% fish - 30% green waste	0.05955

Table 22: H/C ratios

Table 22 shows very similar values of H/C, which are very low, so all the char produced using different amount of seafood waste and green waste could be applied as amendment agent in agriculture. The last test done on the char is the analysis of the metals inside it (49); Figure 59 shows the results coming from such analysis.

Figure 59: ICP-OES test

		Threshold value				Char 100% Gw			Char 70% Gw 30% Fish		Char 50% Gw 50% F	Char 30% Gw 70% F	Char 100% F
		D.Lgs 75/2010	EU 1009/2019	EBC	IBI	20/10/'22	18/11/'22	22/11/'22	06/12/'22	12/12/'22	16/11/'22	15/12/'22	25/10/'22
Na	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	2458	2562	2656	6352	5917	9278	12503	18319
K	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	10930	11532	11277	16767	15193	16205	19453	22689
Mg	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	5763	6301	6313	6798	6617	5500	5349	5094
Ca	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	60404	61588	63747	75546	75007	72397	72104	82444
P	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	2359	2785	2807	15587	15308	26396	33734	60350
Be	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09
Cd	mg/kg	1.5	2	1.5	1.4	<0,34	<0,34	<0,34	<0,34	<0,34	<0,34	<0,34	<0,34
Co	mg/kg	x	x	x	34	2.37	3.62	3.36	3.56	2.72	2.63	2.32	2.80
Cr	mg/kg	x	x	90	93	21.31	26.36	22.15	37.72	22.54	28.12	39.68	33.87
Cu	mg/kg	230	300	100	143	38.07	43.99	45.35	51.92	56.62	63.58	59.41	76.88
Fe	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	4156	5749	4946	5356	4772	3174	2638	1709
Li	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	9.12	11.26	11.70	11.05	11.21	8.53	7.31	3.53
Mn	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	178.7	214.9	231.5	206.9	200.6	144.5	129.6	70.8
Mo	mg/kg	x	x	x	75	7.56	11.03	10.45	10.88	8.05	20.13	21.03	27.94
Ni	mg/kg	100	50	50	47	21.20	<0,12	28.69	36.26	30.67	77.17	59.92	164.79
Pb	mg/kg	140	120	150	121	12.34	19.51	13.59	12.08	15.67	36.74	28.79	70.79
Sr	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	248.6	270.4	279.5	323.5	323.5	315.5	309.3	364.8
Ti	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	83.36	107.22	102.05	91.38	93.26	60.23	46.83	10.12
Tl	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	<4,6	<4,6	<4,5	<4,5	<4,5	<4,5	<4,5	<4,5
V	mg/kg	x	x	x	x	8.23	10.41	9.48	10.13	9.19	6.40	5.36	2.14
Zn	mg/kg	500	800	400	416	137.2	161.0	134.4	169.0	180.6	209.3	237.1	324.9

Table 23: ICP-OES analysis result

*X : there are no standard limit

Considering the tests performed with the same mixture, such as 100% green waste, the values obtained from such analysis are very close each other.

Figure 60: ICP-OES results - Nutrient content vs Seafood waste

Important evidence is shown considering the sodium, potassium, calcium and phosphorus content (Figure 60): they show a linear trend, increasing with the addition of seafood amount inside the biomass to be pyrolyzed. This behaviour is due to the chemical composition of the seafood waste (Suitable feedstocks), since it's a biomass rich in proteins, so with high content of nutrient compared to the green waste.

Another important result coming from the ICP-OES analysis (49) is related to the Nickel amount: the standards have set threshold limit beyond which char cannot be used as a soil improver (Table 5) and, as the seafood waste content within the initial biomass increases (with values higher than 50%), such threshold is exceeded (Figure 61).

Figure 61: ICP-OES results - Nickel content vs Seafood waste

According to the char characterization, the major differences are related to the nutrient content of the seafood waste, which make the char unsuitable as amendment: for this reason, the char is used as additive in composting process.

4.2.3. BIO-OIL CHARACTERIZATION

After the FT-IR analysis, the software shows the IR spectrum with various peaks (3.2.3.2. BIO-OIL ANALYSIS), each of them corresponds to the interaction of the IR of a molecule, so it is possible to identify the composition of the bio-oil. These spectra are elaborated and grouped in order to compare them: in this section are reported the IR spectra.

Figure 62: Comparison between bio-oil coming from 100% GW tests

Figure 62 shows the spectra obtained analyzing the bio-oil produced during the pyrolysis of 100% green waste samples. In particular the following peaks are identified:

- 3375 cm^{-1} : correspond to the group OH of water together with alcohols and carboxylic acids;
- 2965, 2933, 2851 cm^{-1} : corresponding to aliphatic C-H groups;
- 1717 cm^{-1} : C=O carbonyl of aldehydes, esters and/or ketones;
- 1699 cm^{-1} : carbonyl C=O of aromatic groups;
- 1599 cm^{-1} : stretching C-C Aromatic groups;
- 1417 cm^{-1} : aromatic ring stretching, COO group antisymmetric stretching, CH₂ group wagging;
- 1145 cm^{-1} : C-O stretching;
- 1052 cm^{-1} : O-C-C stretching.

From the interpretation of Figure 62, it is possible to see that the three spectra are very similar each other, meaning that they are characterized by the same composition, so this confirms the replicability of the test.

Figure 63: Comparison between bio-oil coming from 100% GW & 100% SF waste tests

Figure 63 shows the comparison between the composition of the bio-oil produced pyrolyzing 100% seafood waste and 100% green waste. Considering the peaks related to the red curve (bio-oil of 100% seafood waste pyrolysis) it's possible to notice:

- 2920 cm⁻¹: asymmetric stretching of methylenes in lipids;
- 2854 cm⁻¹: symmetric stretching of methylenes in lipids;
- 1595 cm⁻¹: C=O stretching of proteins;
- 1664 cm⁻¹: O-H stretching overtone band of water;
- 1460 cm⁻¹: scissoring vibration of the CH₃ and CH₂ groups of lipids;
- 1145 cm⁻¹: stretching vibration of the C-C and C-O groups;
- 1051 cm⁻¹: O-C-C stretching.

These two curves differs in mainly two peaks: the first one related to the water band (3374 cm⁻¹) and the other one related to the lipids content (2920 cm⁻¹ and 2854 cm⁻¹ bands). This differences are justified by the composition of the raw materials: from one side the seafood waste is reach of lipids that make the bio-oil more viscous, and from the other side the green waste which contains lignocellulosic material that led to the production of more watery oil (Functional characterization of raw material).

Figure 64: Comparison between bio-oil coming from different amount of GW & SF waste

Figure 64 shows the comparison between bio-oil produced with different amount of raw materials: they show the same behaviour, the main difference could be seen if we compare the spectra coming from the analysis of the seafood bio-oil because it will be characterized by a higher amount of lipids that lead to different peaks. Another important difference can be seen in the initial part of the spectra, where the yellow line (100% green waste) seems to be more flatter compared to the other spectra containing fats of seafood waste.

4.2.4. SYNGAS CHARACTERIZATION

The syngas collected into the bag is then analyzed according to the methodology explained in 3.2.3.3. SYNGAS ANALYSIS; the results coming from such analysis is shown in the following figure.

Figure 65: Syngas analysis – results

The analysis of syngas shows that for higher amount of seafood inside the initial biomass pyrolyzed, the non-condensable fraction is characterized by higher amount of methane, oxygen and carbon dioxide at expense of carbon oxide content. Some of these gases have calorific value (Table 8), leading to a bit change in the calorific power of the syngas at higher content of seafood waste (Figure 66): with higher calorific power, in real plant it's possible to use that energy in co-generation, reducing the amount of electrical energy request for heating the system.

Figure 66: Syngas analysis - Component %, Calorific power vs Seafood waste amount

4.2.5. MASS BALANCES

After the characterization of the products coming from the pyrolysis process, it's possible to make the mass balances, which are useful tool to understand the performances and the yield of the process (PRODUCT YIELD DETERMINATION). In this chapter are shown the mass balances coming from the elaboration of the previous results.

Figure 67: Mass balance - 100% GW

Figure 68: Mass balance - 50% Seafood waste 50% GW

Figure 69: Mass balance - 30% Seafood waste 70% GW

Figure 70: Mass balance - 70% Seafood waste 30% GW

The mass balances coming from the elaboration of the pyrolysis products analysis, confirm the study available in literature (Product characteristics and use): comparing the four mass balances, it's possible to see how the organic carbon ratio is changing with different raw materials percentage within the different products. In particular, the higher is the amount of green waste in the feedstock, the higher will be the organic carbon inside the char and, when the seafood waste amount is increasing in the feedstock, there is a strongly increase on the bio-oil production at the expense of the char amount.

4.3. Composting performances nuova gennaio

4.3.1. Process monitoring

In this section are reported the results coming from the initial characterization of the raw materials that are used as feedstock for the composting process.

Figure 71: Raw materials for compost: Fish waste - pruning waste - Biochar

Sample	Humidity %	VS	C	H	N	Bulk density	C:N
	%	%TS	%TS	%TS	%TS	kg/L	
Fish waste	75.81	88.03	53.00	8.08	7.52	1.093	7.05
Pruning waste	10.62	90.93	48.00	6.42	2.17	0.137	22.12
Biochar	0.9	72.9	45.7	3.38	0.16	n.d.	285.63
Composting mixture	44.39	91.28	50.70	6.51	3.54	0.302	14.32

Table 24: Characterization of raw materials for composting test

Mixing pruning waste with fish by-products, humidity and C:N ratio were adjusted to optimum range such as 40-60% and 15-30, respectively (Haug, 2018). Fish waste is, indeed, too wet to be used as it is and its C:N is too low, influencing the microbial activity and increasing ammonia volatilization. Metal concentration was also tested on the raw materials (Table 25).

Metal	u.m.	Fish waste	Pruning waste	Biochar	Composting mixture
Na	mg/kg	7939	3175	475	3861
K	mg/kg	6351	6393	2408	6403
Mg	mg/kg	1834	1584	2836	1656
Ca	mg/kg	24828	17297	12926	17830
P	mg/kg	15486	3681	1278	6475
Be	mg/kg	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09	<0,09
Cd	mg/kg	<0,34	<1,1	<1,1	<1,1
Co	mg/kg	<1,8	<1,8	<1,8	<1,8
Cr	mg/kg	3.11	8.94	n.d.	18.79
Cu	mg/kg	48.56	58.40	40.28	50.74
Fe	mg/kg	399.22	1211.80	n.d.	1833.40
Li	mg/kg	1.44	3.34	8.93	3.41
Mn	mg/kg	18.59	40.88	220.17	49.05

Mo	mg/kg	4.41	4.66	5.38	4.55
Ni	mg/kg	6.66	8.16	122.39	15.82
Pb	mg/kg	<2,8	<9,4	18.12	<9,5
Sr	mg/kg	141.09	132.76	61.24	120.62
Ti	mg/kg	7.64	15.68	89.15	15.07
Tl	mg/kg	<4,5	<4,5	<4.5	<4,6
V	mg/kg	0.98	1.13	5.04	1.49
Zn	mg/kg	93	87	n.d.	105

Table 25: Raw materials for compost characterization - ICP results (n.d. not determined values)

Oxygen uptake rate was also measured on initial substrate to evaluate and further monitoring the biological stability of such material (Table 26).

	u.m.	Fish waste		Bulking Agent		Composting mixture	
sample mass	g	9.08	8.99	3.19	3.21	4.69	4.40
ph after 4 h	-	7.21	7.22	7.31	7.29	7.26	7.28
pressure drop	kPa	11.28	10.41	9.44	7.43	9.96	9.75
time interval	h	12.13	10.73	49.00	33.13	21.47	17.27
oxygen consumption	mmolO ₂ /kgVS	1819	1696	1146	896	1268	1323
Oxygen uptake rate	mmolO ₂ /kgVS/h	149.93	158.00	23.38	27.05	59.06	76.64
OUR	mgO ₂ /kgVS/h	4798	5056	748.5	865.6	1890	2452

Table 26: OUR results – raw materials

As expected, fish waste resulted to be a very low biologically stable material meaning suitable for stabilization process like composting (Table 27). Pruning waste is instead a quite stable biomass: it was added to the composting mixture to balance C:N ratio, FAS, humidity and so improve the composting process. Biological stability was then monitored along the testing time, and it could indicate when stop active or maturation phase of composting.

OUR [MGO ₂ /KGV/S/H]	BIOLOGICAL STABILITY
<500	Very high level
500-1000	High level
1000-1500	Medium-high level
1500-3000	Medium-low level
>3000	Very low level. Typical value of biomass rich in biodegradable fractions

Table 27: Classification of biomass stability according to OUR (UNI EN 11184:2016)

During the test, the temperature inside the reactor and the air flux are monitored every 10 minutes with online sensors (Table 10), showing the trend in Figure 72.

Figure 72: Compost results - temperature and flux trend

From Figure 72, it's possible to see that after a few days, there is a strong increase in temperature (up to 60°C), meaning that the thermophilic condition is reached (internal temperature >50°C). This phase is maintained only for one day, then the system is cooled down. In this way, minimum requirements for using compost as CMC for fertiliser production are not respected. Thermophilic conditions are considered as needed conditions to sanitize the initial biomass and so ensure safety use of the final compost avoiding pathogenic risks.

A second temperature peak was reached on the 8th day after being set the air flux equal to 100 l/h (manual regulation). Temperature behaviour gives an indication of the microbial activity inside the system, such as oxygen concentration in the exhausted gas. In Figure 73, the oxygen concentration is mirrored compare the temperature: the higher the temperature, the lower the oxygen exiting the reactor because the microorganisms are using much more oxygen for their metabolism which, in parallel, led to an increase in temperature. Indeed, one of the most used control strategies for aeration management is based on maximum and minimum values of oxygen concentration in the outgoing gases.

Figure 73: Compost results - temperature and oxygen trend

Another important aspect to be monitored is emissions to atmosphere. Composting consumes oxygen, releasing carbon dioxide due to microbial respiration, ammonia due to nitrogen volatilization, methane and nitrogen dioxide due to formation of anaerobic zone where fermentation takes place, and volatile organic compound due to the biomass degradation.

In our test, NH_3 is released after a few days, since it is produced due to the microbial activity which, in the beginning, need to be acclimatized. Figure 74 shows the concentration of ammonia and carbon dioxide as a function of the internal temperature. The CO_2 emissions indicate the respiration of the bacteria inside the reactor: in fact, CO_2 has the same trend of the internal temperature and the opposite of oxygen concentration in exhausted gas. Similarly, ammonia peaks are produced during higher microbial activity.

Figure 74: Compost results - NH_3 and CO_2 trend as function of temperature

At minor extent also VOC were produced. Cumulative emissions are shown in Figure 75

Figure 75: NH_3 and VOC concentrations over time (left) and cumulative emissions (right)

During the compost process, also some GHG were emitted such as methane and nitrogen dioxide with a global warming potential (GWP) of 28 and 265, respectively (IPCC). These gases were

analysed three times per week and Figure 76 shows their trend, strictly related to microbial activity in anaerobic conditions.

Figure 76: Compost results - GHGs trend over time

The higher is the temperature, the higher is the biological activity, resulting in more GHG emissions. In particular, Figure 76 shows higher production of N₂O compared to CH₄.

4.3.2. Compost characterization

A period mixing (at least every week) was necessary because air is injected from the bottom, drying heterogeneously the biomass. After the first week, biomass at the bottom it was drier compared to the top where residual moisture was observed (Figure 77 left).

Figure 77: Composting mixture after 7 days -before (left) and after (right) emptying, mixing and filling

Since the biomass was not able to maintain thermophilic conditions for enough time, after ten days the reactor was emptied and biomass was humidified to reach optimum water content. The initial composting mixture, as well as after the first emptying (7th day), showed 45% of humidity

corresponding to the lower values of suggested optimum range (40-60%). It could be one inhibition factor for microorganism activity. Therefore, 2 L of water was added and mixed to composting mixture before filling again the reactor. Anyway, the temperature remained below 40°C. Biomass transformation during the composting process is summarized in Table 28.

Sample		Humidity	TS	VS	Ash	OUR
		%		%TS	%TS	mmolO ₂ /h/kgVS
Composting mixture	Day zero	44.39	55.61	91.28	8.72	67.85
	After 7 d	45.18	54.82	88.29	11.71	48.79
	After 10 d	61.79*	38.21	87.14	12.86	**
	After 15 d	52.40	47.60	88.95	11.05	31.09

*after humidification ** not measured

Table 28: Characterization of composting mixture along time

From OUR results, a continuous stabilization of composting mixture is demonstrated (Figure 78). Anyway, active phase need at least one more week. Later on, biomass will follow a maturation step without forced aeration but manual turning once per week.

Figure 78: OUR of composting mixture along time

Every day, leachate was opened to collect such liquid. It was characterized mainly to understand the amount of nitrogen lost through leaching (Table 29).

Sample	Moisture %	TS%	TVS%	mg N/l
	%	%	%	4677
13/1/23	98.72	1.28	76.32	5530
14/1/23	98.82	1.18	68.50	4655
16/1/23	98.97	1.03	64.87	4921
18/1/23	99.04	0.96	68.43	7298
19/1/23	97.81	2.19	73.39	3589
23/1/23	97.90	2.10	72.57	5478
24/1/23	97.93	2.07	70.26	5918
25/1/23	97.92	2.08	68.31	5744

Table 29: Leachate characterization

Indeed, we started from a nitrogen-rich biomass (fish waste) and we would like to recover bio-based fertilizer. Therefore it is essential to maximize nutrients (like Nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium) recovery, minimizing hindering phenomena. Two main losses of nitrogen content, during composting, are due to NH_3 volatilization and leachate production. Figure 79 shows nitrogen losses measured during the composting test: almost 5% of the initial nitrogen is lost.

Figure 79: Cumulative nitrogen loss % during compost

Further research are needed to assess the biochar contribution along the composting process. First evidence comparing this trial (“with biochar 2”) with previous experiments show NH_3 reduction with respect to conventional composting of fish waste where biochar was not included. At the same time, similar results were obtained when co-composted biochar is tested.

5. Conclusions

An alternative way to manage fish by-products can be the use of such materials in thermochemical process and composting to recover nutrients to further improve soil characteristics and provide bio-based fertilizers. Valorization of seafood waste into valuable products for agricultural needs is the main objective of the Adriatic Sea Case Study within the SEA2LAND project.

This study was divided into three main parts: i) characterization of the fish by-product, identifying the more appropriate species for the thermochemical processes, ii) experimental tests on pyrolysis with further quantitative and qualitative analysis of biochar, bio-oil and syngas, iii) co-composting of seafood waste and biochar. As the first step, several types of seafood waste were analyzed, starting from mollusc by-products (murex, clams and mussels) and fish waste. TGA carried out in inert atmosphere show low suitability of mollusc waste as pyrolysis biomass since poor in inorganic content. On the contrary fish waste, as well as the commonly used gardening waste, has higher fixed carbon content to be valorized in the final biochar and produced much more gas to be converted in energy for sustain thermochemical process. From the experimental test on pyrolysis carried out in PARR reactor it was possible to investigate the influence of initial feedstock on the pyrolysis yield and characterization of solid, liquid and gas product. The higher the amount of fish by-products (>50%), the higher the bio-oil produced during the test (up to 40%). Through spectroscopy (FT-IR) on bio-oil it was observed higher amount of water molecules when pyrolysis is carried out with a higher amount of green waste. While, higher the seafood waste in the feedstock higher is methane content and lower the carbon oxide in the syngas.

Biochar produced along the experimental activity did not show relevant differences in the pH, ash, C and H content. Major differences were found in the nitrogen (increasing up to 5%) and metal content. In particular, the addition of fish to the feedstock mix increases the final concentration of nickel in biochar up to 164 mg/kg of dry matter: standard quality is not respected using more than 50% of fish waste.

By calculating the mass balance of carbon, results showed that higher the amount of green waste, higher is the amount of carbon stock inside the char, while increasing the seafood contribution more most of carbon is contained in bio-oil.

The final step of this project is the composting process. Fish waste was combined with pruning waste acting as a bulking agent, and with 10% of biochar as a process improver. Thermophilic conditions were reached in few days corresponding to a more active microbial community as indirectly shown from the oxygen concentration in the exhausted gas. To promote microbial community the composting pile was also humidified after 10 days to restore optimum conditions but not relevant differences in the temperature profile were obtained. Ammonia peaks were almost overlapped to temperature peak, as well as CO₂ release due to microorganism respiration. Anyway, specific cumulative emission of ammonia (gNH₃/kg N_{feedstock}), after 15 days, were almost half of that one produced during composting without biochar addition. 5% of nitrogen loss was determined after 2 weeks of composting considering NH₃ volatilization and N lost through leaching. Biological stability of composting mixture decrease along the time, but, as expected, 15 days of active composting were not sufficient to reach stability level set by EU Regulation on Fertilizer 2019/1009 (oxygen uptake rate is lower than 25 mmol O₂/kgVS/h).

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